

FEEDACTIV - Development of functional fish feed based on bioactive compounds of marine and herbal origin

Deliverable D3.1.

Title: Innovative green process of recovery of bioactive compounds from the reference list of edible plants and algae, and evaluation of their extracts in cell series with the desired phytobiotic properties

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	7
2. Selection of edible plants/herbs and algae with antimicrobial and antioxidant action	8
2.1. Creation of a reference list (or database) from bibliographic and other research sources with possible species that meet the desired phyto-biotic properties	8
2.2. Collection of plant/herb and algal specimens	12
2.2.1 Agricultural by-products	13
2.2.2 Microalgae and macroalgae	18
2.2.3 Essential oils	22
3. Recovery of bioactive ingredients from selected plant and algal species through green extraction methods	28
3.1 Raw material processing	28
3.2 Extraction of bioactive compounds from selected plants and herbs - conventional and green methods	30
3.2.1 Conventional extraction method – Soxhlet (S)	30
3.2.2 Green extraction methods	31
3.2.2.1 Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)	31
3.2.2.2 Ultrasound assisted extraction + Microwave assisted extraction (UAE/MAE)	31
3.2.2.3 Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE)	32
3.2.2.4 High-pressure extraction (HPE)	32
3.2.2.5 Hydro-distillation for herbs	32
3.2.3 Optimization of extraction methods of bioactive compounds from selected matrices	33
3.3 Characterization of produced extracts	38
3.3.1 HPLC-DAD-MS-ESI + analysis for identification and quantification of the main compounds of analysed extracts (Agricultural by-products, microalgae)	38
3.3.1.1 HPLC results of citrus matrices	40
3.3.1.2 HPLC results of olive leaves	50
3.3.1.3 HPLC results for bog bilberry	63
3.3.1.4 HPLC results of microalgae	65

3.3.2 GC-MS analysis of essential oil samples	81
3.3.3 Total phenolic content - Agricultural by-products, micro/macroalgae.....	83
3.3.4 Total chlorophyll content – Micro/macroalgae.....	83
3.3.5 Total carotenoid content - Micro/macroalgae	84
3.3.6 Total phycocyanin content.....	86
3.2.7 Total protein content.....	87
3.2.8 Macroalgae – <i>Ulva lactuca</i> (Total carotenoid content, Total phenolic content and Extraction Yield)	90
4. Evaluation of extracts in cell series	98
4.1 Antioxidant activity of analysed extracts	98
4.2 Antibacterial and antifungal activity of analysed extracts.....	104
5. Conclusions	113

List of Abbreviation	
Abbreviation	Explanation
AA	Antioxidant activity
CE	Conventional extraction
DPPH	2,2-diphenyl-picrylhydrazyl
GAE	Gallic acid equivalents
HCA	Hydroxycinnamic acids
HPLC	High-Performance Liquid Chromatography
MAE	Microwave-assisted extraction
MIC	Minimum inhibitory concentration
TCC	Total carotenoid content
UAE	Ultrasound-assisted extraction
TEAC	Trolox equivalents antiradical capacity
TP	Total phenolic
TPC	Total phenolic content/compounds
UAE	Ultrasound-assisted extraction
US	Ultrasound
MAE	Microwave- Ultrasound-assisted extraction
MW	Microwave
PLE	Pressurized liquid extraction technique
HPLC-DAD-ESI-MS	High-performance liquid chromatography equipped with photodiode array detection-mass
ANOVA	One-way analysis of variance

UAE/MAE	Ultrasound/microwave assisted extraction
TPC	Total phenolic content
DM	Dry matter
TFC	Total flavonoid content
US	Ultrasound
MW	Microwave
CFU	Colony-forming units
TSB	Tryptic Soy broth
MH	Mueller-Hinton
LC-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry/ mass spectrometry
GC-MS	Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry
LP	Lemon peel
OP	Orange peel
LP + OP	lemon peel + orange peel
OL	Olive leaves
PMFs	Polymethoxyflavones
EO	Essential oil

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean Basin is globally renowned for its extraordinary biodiversity, characterized by a wide variety of plant and algal species ((Blondel *et al.* 2010). This remarkable ecological richness stems from the region's intricate topography, diverse microclimates, and long-standing interactions between human activities and natural ecosystems (Thompson 2020). These unique environmental factors have led to the evolution of flora with specialized natural defense mechanisms, including antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Wink 2010). Such attributes have captured the interest of researchers seeking innovative and sustainable solutions to pressing challenges in industries such as aquaculture.

Aquaculture is essential for global food security but is increasingly burdened by the overuse of antibiotics in fish farming (FAO 2016). While antibiotics have traditionally been employed to control diseases and enhance fish growth, their excessive use has resulted in the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria (Cabello 2006). This growing issue poses significant risks to human and animal health, as well as to aquatic ecosystems. The search for natural alternatives that can effectively manage diseases while minimizing environmental harm has thus become a critical focus of research (Reverter *et al.* 2014).

One promising solution lies in the use of phytobiotics—bioactive compounds derived from plants and algae (Citarasu 2010). These compounds exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, antiparasitic, and immunomodulatory properties. When incorporated into fish diets, phytobiotics can enhance fish health, reduce disease prevalence, and improve overall productivity (Abd El-latif *et al.* 2021; Dawood 2021). By decreasing reliance on antibiotics, phytobiotics offer a pathway toward more sustainable and environmentally responsible aquaculture practices.

This research aims to identify and characterize phytobiotic compounds from Mediterranean plants and algae that could serve as effective alternatives to antibiotics in aquaculture. The initial phase involves a thorough review of scientific literature to pinpoint plant and algal species with desired bioactive properties (Reverter *et al.* 2014). This information will be consolidated into a comprehensive database, forming the foundation for subsequent investigations.

The next stage focuses on collecting targeted plant, herb, and algal species from their natural habitats, adhering to ethical and sustainable collection practices. Bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, acetophenols, carotenoids, phenolic compounds, fatty acids, and proteins, will then be extracted using environmentally friendly green extraction methods (Chemat *et al.* 2012). These compounds will be evaluated through rigorous testing to determine their antimicrobial, antioxidant, and other health-promoting activities.

Based on these assessments, the most promising phytobiotic candidates will be selected for further investigation. By exploring the vast phytobiotic potential of Mediterranean flora, this research seeks to contribute to the development of sustainable aquaculture practices that address the challenges of antibiotic overuse (FAO 2016; Reverter *et al.* 2014). The findings aim to promote healthier fish populations, mitigate antimicrobial resistance, and support the long-term health of aquatic ecosystems.

2. Selection of edible plants/herbs and algae with antimicrobial and antioxidant action

This chapter explores the selection of specific plants, herbs, and algae with antimicrobial and antioxidant properties that could serve as natural dietary additives for farmed fish. The goal of this project is to reduce or replace antibiotics in aquaculture by incorporating bioactive phytobiotic compounds that promote fish health. This study uses a comprehensive research approach to identify and evaluate at least ten to twelve edible plants, herbs, and marine algae species based on their bioactive potential and sustainability.

2.1. Creation of a reference list (or database) from bibliographic and other research sources with possible species that meet the desired phytobiotic properties

The selection process began with an extensive literature review to create a database (Table 1) of plant and algal species with promising phytobiotic properties. Those marked in green are those that have been selected to be considered for the analyses specified in the project. Following the review, samples were collected for analysis, and four key matrices were identified: agricultural by-products (citrus peels, olive leaves, bog bilberry leaves), microalgae (spirulina and chlorella), macroalgae (*Ulva lactuca*) and essential oils (garlic, thyme, conehead thyme, eucalyptus, and rosemary). These matrices were selected for their bioactive compounds and suitability for fish diets.

Citrus peels, particularly lemon (*Citrus limon*) and orange (*Citrus sinensis*), emerged as a potent source of flavonoids, phenolic acids, essential oils, and carotenoids. These compounds exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties, supporting their use as natural additives. Lemon peels (LP) are rich in eriocitrin and hesperidin, while orange peels (OP) contain high levels of naringin and limonene. Their bioactive profiles make them ideal candidates for sustainable valorization in aquaculture and beyond.

Marine algae, such as spirulina (*Arthrospira platensis*) and chlorella (*Chlorella vulgaris*), were identified for their high protein content, carotenoids, chlorophyll, and phenolic compounds. Spirulina is notable for phycocyanin, a pigment with potent

antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, while chlorella is rich in chlorophyll and carotenoids like lutein and zeaxanthin. These algae are widely recognized for their immune-boosting and growth-promoting effects, making them suitable for aquafeed. Essential oils from garlic (*Allium sativum*), thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus globulus*), and rosemary (*Salvia rosmarinus*) were selected for their potent antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. Compounds such as allicin, thymol, carvacrol, and eucalyptol contribute to their efficacy against fish pathogens and their potential as natural preservatives in aquafeed.

Table 1. Selection of plant matrices with biological activities

Common name	Scientific name	Active substance	Therapeutic properties	References
Rosemary	<i>Salvia rosmarinus</i>	Cineole	reduces mortality against Streptococcus, digestion, antiseptic, antioxidant	Nieto <i>et al.</i> 2018; Jan <i>et al.</i> 2017; Moss and Oliver 2012.
Oregano	<i>Origanum vulgare</i>	Oregano essential oil (OEO)	resistance to <i>Listonella anguillarum</i> , improves growth & immunity; antimicrobial	Alagawany <i>et al.</i> 2020; Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2020.
Garlic	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Allicin	against bacterial diseases, digestion stimulant, antiseptic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	El-Saber Batiha <i>et al.</i> 2020; Ankri and Mirelman 1999; Amagase 2006; Pashaki <i>et al.</i> 2020; Nya and Austin 2009
Cardamom	<i>Elattaria cardamomum</i>	Cineole	appetite and digestion stimulant	Cheikhoussef <i>et al.</i> 2023
Parsley	<i>Petroselinum crispum</i>	Apiol	antiseptic, appetite and digestion stimulant	El-Houseiny <i>et al.</i> 2022
Clove	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Eugenol	antiseptic, appetite and digestion stimulant	Brum <i>et al.</i> 2017; Rattanachai kunso pon, P. and Phumkhachorn, P. 2009; Saeed <i>et al.</i> 2022
Thyme, Conehead thyme	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>; <i>Thymus capitatus</i>	Thymol	antiseptic, antioxidant, digestion stimulant	Adorjan and Buchbauer 2010; Ghanbari <i>et al.</i> 2012; Salehi <i>et al.</i> 2018)
Eucalyptus	<i>Eucalyptus</i>	Eucalyptol	antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory	Silva <i>et al.</i> 2003

Table 1. Selection of plant matrices with biological activities

Common name	Scientific name	Active substance	Therapeutic properties	References
Peppermint	<i>Mentha x piperita</i>	Menthol	antiseptic, appetite and digestion stimulant	Adel <i>et al.</i> 2016
Olive tree (leaf extract)	<i>Olea europaea</i>	Polyphenols	growth performance, antioxidant, antibacterial, antimicrobial,	Reverter <i>et al.</i> 2014
Citrus (peel)	<i>Citrus</i> (genus)	Polyphenols Sweet orange peel - 83% limonene	antioxidant	Reverter <i>et al.</i> 2014; Li <i>et al.</i> 2009; Xu <i>et al.</i> 2007
Bog bilberry (leaf extract)	<i>Vaccinium uliginosum</i> L.	flavonoids (e.g., quercetin, kaempferol), phenolic acids (e.g., chlorogenic acid), and tannins	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and antifungal effects	Häkkinen and Törrönen 2000; Skrovankova <i>et al.</i> 2015
Spirulina	<i>Arthrospira spp.</i>	Phycocyanin & γ - linoleic acid	improves growth, immunity, feed efficiency, brighter coloration	Karkos <i>et al.</i> 2011
Chlorella	<i>Chlorella</i> (genus)	Carotenoids, phenolic compounds	Immunostimulant, antioxidant	Li <i>et al.</i> 2007; Matos <i>et al.</i> 2017)
Sea lettuce	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	Fucoidan (FCD)	growth-promoting, antioxidant, and immunostimulant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial	Holdt and Kraan 2011 Wong and Cheung 2000; MacArtain <i>et al.</i> 2007
Jerusalem artichoke (topinambur)	<i>Helianthus tuberosus</i>	Polyphenols	antimicrobial properties	Ali <i>et al.</i> 2017
Tea tree	<i>Melaleuca alternifolia</i>	Terpinen-4-ol	antimicrobial properties	Liu <i>et al.</i> 2022

Table 1. Selection of plant matrices with biological activities

Common name	Scientific name	Active substance	Therapeutic properties	References
Kelp	<i>Ascophylum nodosum</i>	phlorotannins and unique polysaccharides: alginic acid (28%), fucoidans (11.6%), mannitol (7.5%), and laminarin (4.5%)	antimicrobial properties	Frazzini <i>et al.</i> 2022; Shukla <i>et al.</i> 2019

2.2. Collection of plant/herb and algal specimens

The collection of samples was carried out according to the correct practices of collecting plants/herbs (guide for collecting aromatic and medicinal plants) and was accompanied by the necessary data, such as taxonomic information, locating plants with geographical information system (GPS), and part of the plant collected (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Matrices selection

2.2.1 Agricultural by-products

→ Citrus peel

Taxonomic information

- **Lemon (*Citrus limon*):**
 - **Kingdom:** Plantae
 - **Clade:** Angiosperms
 - **Order:** Sapindales
 - **Family:** Rutaceae
 - **Genus:** Citrus
 - **Species:** *Citrus limon*
 - **Common Name:** Lemon
- **Orange (*Citrus sinensis*):**
 - **Kingdom:** Plantae
 - **Clade:** Angiosperms
 - **Order:** Sapindales
 - **Family:** Rutaceae
 - **Genus:** Citrus
 - **Species:** *Citrus sinensis*
 - **Common Name:** Sweet Orange

Lemons and oranges both belong to the genus *Citrus* within the Rutaceae family—a group that includes other economically important fruits such as limes, grapefruits, and tangerines (Manners 2007). *Citrus limon* (lemon) and *Citrus sinensis* (sweet orange) are widely cultivated species valued for their fruits, which provide not only acidic juice but also peels rich in bioactive compounds (Nogata *et al.* 2006; González-Molina *et al.* 2010).

Global distribution and cultivation conditions

Lemons are primarily grown in Mediterranean regions (Italy, Spain, Turkey), as well as in parts of the Americas (e.g., California, Florida, Argentina, Brazil) and Asia (India, China), capitalizing on climates with mild winters and warm, dry summers. Oranges, meanwhile, are extensively cultivated in subtropical and tropical zones including Brazil, the United States (Florida, California), Spain, China, and India. These regions provide the warmth and sunlight essential for fruit development and high-quality yields (FAO 2018).

Key factors influencing citrus growth include suitable temperature ranges, balanced soil pH and nutrient content, proper drainage, adequate rainfall or irrigation, and favorable topography that ensures good sunlight exposure and water management.

Part of the plant collected

For extraction of bioactive compounds, the peel is the primary part of the citrus fruit utilized. The peel consists of two layers:

- **Flavedo (outer colored layer):** Rich in essential oils, carotenoids, and polymethoxyflavones (PMFs) like nobiletin and tangeretin. These compounds contribute to aromatic quality, antioxidant activity (AA), and antimicrobial properties.
- **Albedo (inner white pith):** Abundant in pectin, hesperidin, naringin, and other flavonoids. The albedo's fiber and polysaccharides offer functional benefits in food formulation and prebiotic applications (Nogata *et al.* 2006; González-Molina *et al.* 2010).

Citrus peels, representing about half of the fruit mass, are often by-products of juice processing. Rather than discarding them or using them solely as animal feed, their valorization for bioactive compounds adds economic and environmental value.

Bioactive compounds in citrus peel

Citrus peels are a rich source of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, essential oils, pectins, and carotenoids. These constituents have been widely studied for their potential antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities (Li *et al.* 2009; Xu *et al.* 2007). OP, for instance, contain abundant hesperidin and naringin, while LP are notably high in eriocitrin. Both lemon and orange peels also feature PMFs (e.g., nobiletin) and phenolic acids (e.g., caffeic, ferulic) that enhance their functional properties.

These phenolic compounds support cardiovascular health, modulate lipid and glucose metabolism, and show promise in cancer prevention. Additionally, their antimicrobial properties can inhibit pathogenic bacteria and fungi, making citrus peel extracts suitable as natural preservatives and functional ingredients in food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic applications.

In aquaculture, incorporating citrus peel extracts into fish diets can help control pathogenic microbes and improve immune responses, thereby supporting sustainable, antibiotic-free fish farming practices. This approach aligns with efforts to reduce antibiotic use and maintain healthy aquatic ecosystems (Reverter *et al.* 2014). Lemon and orange peels exhibit significant antimicrobial properties that can serve as natural alternatives to synthetic antibiotics in fish feed. These compounds have demonstrated effective antibacterial and antifungal activities against common fish pathogens, such as *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio* species, which are responsible for diseases in aquaculture. Incorporating citrus peel extracts in fish diets not only helps inhibit harmful bacterial growth but also enhances the immune response of fish by reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, leading to improved overall health, growth performance, and survival rates. This natural approach in aquafeed supports sustainable and antibiotic-free aquaculture practices, reducing the risk of antibiotic resistance and chemical residues in fish products.

Lemon (Citrus x limon) and orange (Citrus x sinensis) peels and a mixture of them were purchased from a local market in Cluj-Napoca, Romania. The fruits were

imported from Italy and Spain.

→ **Olive leaves (OL)**

Taxonomic information

Scientific name: *Olea europaea*

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Angiosperms

Order: Lamiales

Family: Oleaceae

Genus: *Olea*

Species: *Olea europaea*

Common name: Olive

The olive tree (*Olea europaea*) is a member of the Oleaceae family, which includes over 600 species of trees and shrubs (Boskou 2015; Gorzynik-Debicka *et al.* 2018). Among these, *Olea europaea* is the most economically and agriculturally important species due to its oil-rich fruits (olives), primarily used to produce olive oil. Although OL contain lower levels of oil, they are valuable for their high concentration of bioactive compounds such as oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol, and flavonoids. These compounds exhibit notable antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, making OL beneficial for supplements, functional foods, and cosmetics (de Oliveira *et al.* 2024; Pereira *et al.* 2007).

Global distribution

The primary cultivation area for olives is the Mediterranean region, including Spain, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Tunisia, where hot, dry summers and mild, rainy winters create optimal conditions for olive growth (Boskou 2015). Olive cultivation also extends to non-Mediterranean regions with similar climates, such as California (USA), South Africa, Chile, and Australia.

Parameters for olive cultivation:

- **Climate:** Olive trees thrive in climates with mild winters and long, warm, and dry summers. Adequate but not excessive rainfall and long-term climate data ensure regions consistently meet these conditions.
- **Soil quality:** Ideal soils are well-drained, slightly alkaline to neutral in pH, and balanced in mineral content to support healthy root development and good yields.
- **Water resources:** Although drought-tolerant, olives benefit from reliable water sources. Sustainable irrigation and water-management practices help maintain productivity, especially in arid or semi-arid regions.
- **Topography and Slope:** Gently sloping terrains improve drainage and sunlight exposure. Proper slope assessment prevents erosion, supports mechanized operations, and ensures adequate light penetration to the trees.

Part of the plant collected

For pharmaceutical and nutraceutical applications, OL are the primary part collected due to their rich bioactive profile. They can be harvested as by-products during the olive fruit harvest or collected separately for commercial extraction of beneficial compounds (de Oliveira *et al.* 2024).

Bioactive compounds in olive leaves

Oleuropein is the most abundant and biologically significant compound in OL, offering antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and cardioprotective benefits (Gorzynik-Debicka *et al.* 2018). Hydroxytyrosol and tyrosol also provide potent antioxidant effects, contributing to cardiovascular health. Flavonoids such as luteolin, apigenin, and rutin enhance the leaves' antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. OL are typically dried, ground, and processed to extract these bioactive compounds for use in supplements, cosmetics, and functional foods.

Notably, when included in fish feed, OL extracts rich in compounds like oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol have demonstrated antibiotic-like effects, targeting common fish pathogens such as *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio* species (Reverter *et al.* 2014). These extracts also enhance the fish immune system by improving antioxidant defences and reducing inflammation. Thus, OLE serves as a natural alternative to synthetic antibiotics in aquaculture, supporting sustainable production and reducing the risk of antibiotic resistance.

Natural Food Additives G.P, Athens, Greece, supplied olive tree (Olea europaea, greek cv. Kolovi) leaves.

→ Bog bilberry leaves

Vaccinium uliginosum L. (bog bilberry) is a wild bush indigenous to many parts of the Northern Hemisphere, particularly at higher altitudes in Asia, and in North America and Europe. This small shrub is circumpolar in the Arctic and boreal regions, and it grows on moist and acidic ground, and many different types of wildlife animals consume both the leaves and the fruits. The fruits of *V. uliginosum* are characterized by the presence of anthocyanins and flavonols. Bog bilberries have a distinct flavonol and anthocyanidin profile compared to other *Vaccinium* berries. As a result, it appears that their phenolic profile could be utilized to distinguish them from other berries.

Taxonomic information

Scientific name: *Vaccinium uliginosum*

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Angiosperms

Order: Ericales

Family: Ericaceae

Genus: *Vaccinium*

Species: *Vaccinium uliginosum*

Common names: Bog bilberry, Bog blueberry, Northern bilberry

The bog bilberry (*Vaccinium uliginosum*) belongs to the family Ericaceae, which includes other berry-producing shrubs such as blueberries and cranberries. This genus is renowned for species adapted to cold and acidic environments, and bog bilberry, in particular, is known for its edible berries, which are rich in antioxidants and other beneficial phytochemicals (Häkkinen and Törrönen 2000; Skrovankova *et al.* 2015).

Global distribution and habitat conditions

Bog bilberry is typically found in northern and subarctic regions across Europe, Asia, and North America. It grows in the boreal and tundra zones and thrives in cool, moist, and acidic soils, often associated with bogs, wetlands, and alpine areas. Primary distribution areas include Scandinavia, the British Isles, and Russia, as well as northern parts of Siberia, northeastern China, northern Canada, Alaska, and the northeastern United States (Vander Kloet 1988; Morin *et al.* 2015). Ideal habitat parameters for bog bilberry include:

- **Climate:** Cool temperatures with adequate precipitation.
- **Soil conditions:** Acidic, nutrient-poor soils typical of bogs and wetlands.
- **Altitude:** Frequently found in alpine or tundra zones with cooler microclimates.

Part of the plant collected and bioactive compounds

The leaves of bog bilberry (*Vaccinium uliginosum*) are rich in bioactive compounds that provide various health-promoting properties. Key constituents include flavonoids (e.g., quercetin, kaempferol), phenolic acids (e.g., chlorogenic acid), and tannins, all of which exhibit potent antioxidant activities. These compounds can help neutralize free radicals, reduce oxidative stress, and potentially lower the risk of chronic diseases (Häkkinen and Törrönen 2000; Skrovankova *et al.* 2015). The leaves also contain iridoids, such as monotropein and neomyrtillin, noted for their anti-inflammatory and antidiabetic effects, including the regulation of blood glucose levels.

Tannins present in bog bilberry leaves have astringent properties, historically used to address gastrointestinal issues. Together, these bioactive compounds support potential applications of bog bilberry leaves in natural health products and herbal remedies aimed at managing inflammation, diabetes, and cardiovascular health.

Potential in aquaculture

Bog bilberry leaf extracts, with their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, have shown promise as natural additives in fish feed. Flavonoids, phenolic acids, and tannins in the leaves exhibit antibacterial and antifungal effects, targeting common aquatic pathogens like *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio* species. When included in fish diets, these extracts can reduce pathogen load and enhance the fish immune system, offering an alternative to synthetic antibiotics. This approach mitigates the risk of antibiotic resistance and supports more sustainable and healthy fish farming practices (Puupponen-Pimiä *et al.* 2005; Reverter *et al.* 2014).

The leaves of *V. uliginosum* L. were harvested in the autumn of 2023 from the spontaneous wild flora of 12 Apostoli, Suceava county, Romania.

2.2.2 Microalgae and macroalgae

→ Spirulina

Taxonomic information

Scientific name: *Arthrospira platensis*

Kingdom: Bacteria

Phylum: Cyanobacteria

Class: Cyanophyceae

Order: Oscillatoriales

Family: Microcoleaceae

Genus: Arthrospira

Species: *Arthrospira platensis*

Common name: Spirulina

Arthrospira platensis, commonly known as spirulina, is a filamentous cyanobacterium rather than a true alga, despite its photosynthetic ability and “blue-green” appearance (Habib and Hasan 2008; Borowitzka 2009). It is highly regarded for its rich nutritional profile, including a high protein content, essential amino acids, vitamins, and antioxidants, which have led to its widespread use as a dietary supplement.

Global distribution and cultivation

Spirulina (*A. platensis*) naturally occurs in warm, alkaline waters in tropical and subtropical regions, including Lake Chad in Africa and certain lakes in India, China, and Central America. These environments—characterized by ample sunlight, high temperatures, and alkaline pH—favor its growth (Habib and Hasan 2008). In Europe, while Spirulina does not naturally occur in freshwater lakes, it is commercially cultivated in countries with Mediterranean climates such as Spain, Italy, France, and Greece. Here, controlled systems like outdoor ponds and photobioreactors maintain optimal conditions (temperature, pH, and sunlight) for spirulina cultivation. Commercial production also extends to the United States, India, and Mexico, reflecting its global economic importance as a functional food resource (Belay 1997).

Parameters for spirulina cultivation

- **Temperature:** Ideal growth occurs between 30–40°C.
- **Water pH:** Alkaline conditions (pH 8–11) support optimal productivity.
- **Sunlight:** High levels of sunlight enhance photosynthesis and growth.
- **Water salinity and mineral content:** Moderate to high salinity and a mineral composition similar to natural habitats benefit spirulina biomass production.

For commercial and nutritional use, the entire spirulina biomass is harvested, filtered, washed, and dried. The dried product—available as powder, flakes, or tablets—is rich in high-quality protein, essential fatty acids (including gamma-linolenic acid), vitamins

(notably B vitamins and vitamin E), minerals (iron, magnesium, calcium), and various antioxidants (Borowitzka 2009; Henrikson 2010). Its complete amino acid profile and excellent digestibility make it particularly valuable as a protein source for vegetarians and vegans.

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

Spirulina's bioactive compounds include phycocyanin, a blue pigment with potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Phycocyanin may reduce oxidative stress, support immune function, and has shown potential anticancer and neuroprotective effects (Karkos *et al.* 2011). Spirulina also contains essential fatty acids like gamma-linolenic acid (GLA), beneficial for inflammatory conditions and cardiovascular health, as well as carotenoids (beta-carotene, zeaxanthin) and chlorophyll, which offer antioxidant, detoxifying, and antimicrobial activities.

Polysaccharides and phenolic compounds in Spirulina enhance immune responses and may function as prebiotics, supporting beneficial gut microbiota. Saponins also contribute to its cholesterol-lowering and immune-modulating properties (Habib and Hasan 2008).

Applications in aquaculture

Including spirulina in fish feed has demonstrated antibiotic-like effects, enhancing disease resistance and overall health in aquaculture. The bioactive compounds in Spirulina, such as phycocyanin and phenolic acids, exert antimicrobial actions against common fish pathogens like *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio species*. Additionally, its antioxidants and anti-inflammatory properties support the fish immune system, reduce mortality, and promote growth. By using spirulina as a natural additive, aquaculture can decrease reliance on synthetic antibiotics, mitigating the risk of antibiotic resistance and improving sustainability (Reverter *et al.* 2014).

→ Chlorella

Taxonomic information

Scientific name: Chlorella spp. (notably *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella pyrenoidosa*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Chlorophyta

Class: Trebouxiophyceae

Order: Chlorellales

Family: Chlorellaceae

Genus: Chlorella

Common name: Chlorella

Chlorella is a single-celled green microalga known for its high nutrient content and bioactive compounds, including chlorophyll, proteins, vitamins, and antioxidants, which contribute to its use as a dietary supplement and in functional foods (Becker 2007; Torzillo and Vonshak 2013).

Global distribution and cultivation

Chlorella naturally occurs in freshwater environments—ponds, lakes, and rivers—worldwide. Although native to East Asia, it adapts to diverse climates and water bodies, making it challenging to pinpoint specific natural locations. Regions like Japan, Taiwan, and China are known for their natural occurrence and cultivation of chlorella, while certain freshwater bodies in Central and Eastern Europe, the United States, and Canada also host wild populations. However, most commercially utilized chlorella is cultivated in controlled conditions, such as photobioreactors and outdoor ponds, allowing precise management of parameters like temperature, pH, and nutrient availability (Spolaore *et al.* 2006; Pulz and Gross 2004).

Harvesting and nutrient profile

Chlorella is harvested as a whole-cell biomass, separated from the culture medium by processes like centrifugation. The cells are then dried and processed into powders, tablets, or extracts. This approach retains essential nutrients, including a high protein content (50-60% of dry weight), essential amino acids (lysine, leucine, valine, arginine), essential fatty acids, chlorophyll, carotenoids, vitamins (B-complex, C, E), and minerals (iron, magnesium, calcium) (Becker 2007; Pulz and Gross 2004).

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

Chlorella's protein profile makes it comparable to other high-quality sources such as spirulina. Its chlorophyll content not only imparts a rich green hue but also provides antioxidant benefits. Carotenoids (lutein, zeaxanthin, beta-carotene) offer protection against oxidative stress and support eye health, while beta-carotene can be converted to vitamin A, benefiting immune function and skin health (Matos *et al.* 2017).

Polysaccharides, including β -glucans, exhibit immunomodulatory and anti-inflammatory effects, potentially influencing cholesterol metabolism and supporting heart health. Chlorella is also among the few plant sources of bioavailable vitamin B12, making it valuable for vegetarians and vegans who are at risk of deficiency (Watanabe *et al.* 2014). Essential fatty acids, such as alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), and phenolic compounds (caffeic, ferulic, chlorogenic acids) further contribute to its cardiovascular and anti-inflammatory benefits (Li *et al.* 2007; Matos *et al.* 2017).

Chlorella Growth Factor (CGF), rich in nucleic acids, peptides, polysaccharides, and vitamins, is believed to stimulate cellular repair and regeneration, supporting immune health and recovery (Kay 1991).

Applications in aquaculture

Chlorella demonstrates antibiotic-like properties in fish feed, enhancing disease resistance and overall health in aquaculture. Its antimicrobial compounds, including chlorophyll, polysaccharides, and phenolic acids, help inhibit pathogens like *Aeromonas* and *Vibrio* species. By strengthening the immune response in fish, reducing infection incidence, and improving survival, chlorella reduces reliance on synthetic antibiotics, thus supporting sustainable practices and mitigating antibiotic

resistance (Reverter *et al.* 2014).

→ **Ulva**

Taxonomic information

Scientific name: *Ulva spp.* (notably *Ulva lactuca* and *Ulva intestinalis*)

Kingdom: Plantae

Division: Chlorophyta (Green Algae)

Class: Ulvophyceae

Order: Ulvales

Family: Ulvaceae

Genus: *Ulva*

Common name: Sea lettuce

Ulva, commonly known as sea lettuce, is a green macroalga found worldwide in marine environments and valued for its bioactive compounds, which have applications in aquaculture, biofuel, nutrition, and pharmaceuticals (Holdt and Kraan 2011; MacArtain *et al.* 2007).

Global distribution and habitat conditions

Ulva species are distributed globally in intertidal and shallow subtidal zones along coasts, where they attach to rocks, shells, and other surfaces. They thrive in nutrient-rich environments and often occur in areas with high light availability, including coastlines of the North Sea, the Mediterranean, and the Atlantic. They can be found along the coasts of the United Kingdom, France, and the Mediterranean basin, as well as on Atlantic and Pacific coastlines from New England to California, and in coastal areas of Japan, Korea, and China. *Ulva* is also abundant in Australian and New Zealand coastal ecosystems, particularly in estuarine and nearshore environments. Its wide distribution and tolerance of varied salinity and temperature conditions enable adaptation to numerous coastal habitats (Holdt and Kraan 2011).

Harvesting and nutrient profile

The entire thallus (leaf-like structure) of *ulva* is harvested for commercial purposes. This leafy part contains high levels of bioactive compounds—proteins, polysaccharides, vitamins, and minerals—making it valuable for use in dietary supplements, animal feed, and even bioplastics. After collection, thalli are often dried and processed into powders, extracts, or whole dried products (Wong and Cheung 2000; MacArtain *et al.* 2007).

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

A key bioactive component in *ulva* is its sulfated polysaccharide, ulvan, composed of sugars such as rhamnose, xylose, and glucuronic acid. Ulvan imparts antioxidant, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory properties and exhibits immunomodulatory effects beneficial for human and animal health. It has potential applications in wound healing and skincare due to its cell-stimulating properties (Lahaye and Robic 2007). *Ulva*

contains 15–25% protein by dry weight, featuring essential amino acids like methionine, lysine, and tryptophan. These proteins enhance immune function and are particularly valuable in plant-based diets due to their complete amino acid profile. Bioactive peptides from *Ulva* also contribute to its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (MacArtain *et al.* 2007).

Though present in smaller amounts, phenolic compounds in *ulva* (e.g., catechol, hydroxytyrosol) offer antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects. These phenolics help *Ulva* cope with environmental stressors and may reduce oxidative stress when included in diets (Holdt and Kraan 2011).

Ulva is rich in vitamins (C, A from beta-carotene, B1, B2, and B3) essential for energy production and nervous system function, as well as minerals like calcium, magnesium, iron, potassium, and iodine. These minerals support bone health, muscle function, metabolism, blood health, and thyroid function. Although *ulva* contains only a small amount of lipids, it includes beneficial polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as omega-3 fatty acids like alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), contributing to anti-inflammatory and cardiovascular benefits (Wong and Cheung 2000; MacArtain *et al.* 2007).

In addition to beta-carotene, *ulva* contains lutein and zeaxanthin, carotenoids that provide antioxidant protection for the eyes. These compounds help shield the retina from oxidative damage, potentially reducing the risk of macular degeneration and supporting overall eye health (Holdt and Kraan 2011).

2.2.3 Essential oils

→ Garlic oil

Scientific Name: *Allium sativum*

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Asparagales

Family: Amaryllidaceae

Genus: *Allium*

Common Name: Garlic

Garlic essential oil is extracted from the cloves of *Allium sativum*, a plant recognized for its bioactive sulfur compounds—most notably allicin—which exhibit strong antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties. These attributes make garlic essential oil a popular ingredient in health supplements, natural therapies, and food preservation (Ankri and Mirelman 1999; El-Saber Batiha *et al.* 2020).

Source and production

The garlic essential oil referenced here is sourced from a local producer in Greece, a country with a longstanding tradition of garlic cultivation. Greek garlic is recognized for its distinctive profile of bioactive compounds. The oil is typically produced through steam distillation of garlic cloves, concentrating the sulfur compounds responsible for

its pungent aroma and therapeutic potency (Alexopoulos *et al.* 2011).

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

The main bioactive compound in garlic essential oil is allicin, a sulfur compound that imparts garlic's characteristic odor and therapeutic effects. Other sulfur-containing compounds, such as diallyl disulfide and diallyl trisulfide, also contribute to its health benefits. Allicin exhibits potent antimicrobial properties against various bacteria, fungi, and viruses, making it an effective natural preservative in food and cosmetics. Diallyl disulfide and diallyl trisulfide function as strong antioxidants, reducing oxidative stress and inflammation, and supporting heart health. Additionally, garlic's bioactive compounds bolster immune function, helping the body resist infections (Ankri and Mirelman 1999; Amagase 2006).

Applications in aquaculture and food systems

Garlic essential oil has demonstrated benefits in aquaculture when used as a natural supplement in fish feed. Its antimicrobial properties help reduce pathogen load in fish, enhancing disease resistance without relying on synthetic antibiotics. This promotes sustainable aquaculture practices and mitigates the risk of antibiotic resistance. The antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects of garlic oil further support fish health and growth (Pashaki *et al.* 2020; Nya and Austin 2009).

Nutritional and functional profile

Garlic essential oil, while low in fat, is rich in sulfur compounds and antioxidants that protect cells from oxidative damage and support overall health. Its strong antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory actions make it valuable in functional foods, nutraceuticals, and complementary medicine (El-Saber Batiha *et al.* 2020).

→ **Rosemary essential oil**

Scientific name: *Rosmarinus officinalis*

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: Rosmarinus

Common name: Rosemary

Rosemary essential oil, extracted from *Rosmarinus officinalis*, is supplied by Chiron Kentavros-Greek Organic Herbs, a reputable producer based in Greece. Renowned for its robust antioxidant, antimicrobial, and stimulating properties, this essential oil is a versatile natural ingredient widely used in health, wellness, and personal care products (Nieto *et al.* 2018; Jan *et al.* 2017). Sourced from Greece, where the Mediterranean climate supports the growth of aromatic rosemary plants, the oil is obtained through steam distillation of the flowering tops. This process concentrates the volatile compounds responsible for rosemary oil's distinctive herbal aroma and therapeutic benefits (Yang *et al.* 2023).

Primary active components and their effects

The main bioactive compounds in rosemary essential oil include cineole (1,8-cineole), α -pinene, camphor, borneol, p-cymene, verbenone, and linalool. Cineole supports respiratory health, provides antimicrobial activity, and enhances mental clarity (Moss and Oliver 2012). α -Pinene offers a fresh, woody aroma and mild anti-inflammatory effects. Camphor delivers analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, making it useful for easing muscle and joint discomfort. Borneol contributes antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory actions, while p-cymene adds antioxidant and antimicrobial activity. Verbenone supports skin rejuvenation and respiratory health. Linalool imparts a calming effect, reducing stress and promoting relaxation (Nieto *et al.* 2018; Jan *et al.* 2017).

Therapeutic benefits

Rosemary essential oil offers a broad range of therapeutic advantages. It improves cognitive function by enhancing focus, memory, and mental clarity, making it popular in aromatherapy for reducing stress and increasing concentration (Moss and Oliver 2012). As a natural decongestant, it helps clear airways and alleviate symptoms of colds and respiratory discomfort. Its antimicrobial and antifungal properties inhibit the growth of bacteria and fungi, supporting its use in natural cleaning products and personal care formulations. Rosemary's anti-inflammatory effects reduce muscle and joint inflammation, providing relief from aches and stiffness. The oil also supports hair growth, reduces dandruff, and improves scalp health, making it widely used in shampoos and conditioners (Maurya *et al.* 2021; Panahi *et al.* 2015).

Versatile applications and sustainability

Highly versatile, rosemary essential oil finds applications in aromatherapy, personal care, animal care, and household use. Its refreshing and stimulating aroma enhances alertness and reduces fatigue. Its inclusion in skin and hair care products imparts soothing, rejuvenating effects, while in animal care, it serves as a natural antimicrobial and insect repellent. In household settings, it acts as a natural disinfectant and odor neutralizer, offering a sustainable alternative to synthetic additives. Rosemary essential oil's potency and effectiveness stem from its high concentration of cineole, camphor, and other active terpenes, ensuring its utility across various domains (Nieto *et al.* 2018; Jan *et al.* 2017).

→ Eucalyptus oil

Scientific name: *Eucalyptus globulus*

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Myrtales

Family: Myrtaceae

Genus: *Eucalyptus*

Common name: Eucalyptus

Known for its potent respiratory and antimicrobial properties, eucalyptus oil is widely used in natural therapies, health products, and as a refreshing and purifying agent in cleaning and personal care products (Cermelli *et al.* 2008; Sadlon and Lamson 2010). Sourced from Greece, where the warm, dry climate promotes high concentrations of the active compound eucalyptol, the oil is obtained through steam distillation of eucalyptus leaves. This process captures the volatile compounds that give eucalyptus oil its distinctive, invigorating aroma and medicinal effects.

Primary active components and their effects

The primary active component of eucalyptus oil is eucalyptol (1,8-cineole), a terpene well-documented for its anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and decongestant properties (Silva *et al.* 2003). Other terpenes, such as limonene and α -pinene, complement these benefits. Eucalyptol acts as a natural decongestant, relieving symptoms of coughs, sinus congestion, and respiratory discomfort. Limonene contributes AA, enhancing the oil's antimicrobial profile. α -Pinene supports respiratory health and imparts a fresh, pine-like aroma while providing mild anti-inflammatory effects.

Therapeutic benefits

Eucalyptus essential oil offers a range of therapeutic effects supporting respiratory and immune health. Its antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory actions help inhibit the growth of bacteria, fungi, and viruses, making it a useful addition to natural cleaning products and disinfectants (Dorman and Deans 2000). By reducing inflammation in both respiratory and muscular systems, eucalyptus oil can alleviate joint pain and muscle soreness. Its invigorating aroma enhances alertness, improves mental clarity, and is commonly used in aromatherapy.

Applications in animal care and beyond

Eucalyptus essential oil is increasingly used in animal care products due to its natural antimicrobial and insect-repelling properties, providing a sustainable alternative to synthetic treatments. Incorporating it into animal bedding or using it as a spray in barns helps control pests and promotes respiratory health in livestock environments (Khalil *et al.* 2024). While not typically ingested, its unique blend of volatile compounds delivers valuable therapeutic and sensory benefits. The high eucalyptol content underscores its strong respiratory and antimicrobial effects and its suitability for household, animal care, and health-related applications.

→ Thyme essential oil

Scientific name: *Thymus vulgaris*

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: Thymus

Common Name: Thyme

Thyme essential oil, extracted from the leaves and flowering tops of *Thymus vulgaris*, is well-known for its bioactive properties, particularly its antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects. The oil's activity is attributed to its phenolic compounds, primarily thymol and carvacrol, which are widely used in pharmaceuticals, food preservation, and sustainable aquaculture practices (Burt 2004; Hyldgaard *et al.* 2012).

Source and production

The thyme essential oil referenced here was derived from thyme plants cultivated in Greece. The region's Mediterranean climate, with abundant sunlight and well-drained soil, contributes to the synthesis of bioactive compounds such as thymol and carvacrol. The oil was extracted using steam distillation, a technique that preserves the integrity of these volatile compounds (Adorjan and Buchbauer 2010).

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

Thyme essential oil contains a range of active compounds, with thymol and carvacrol being the most prominent:

Thymol: a phenolic compound known for its strong antimicrobial properties, thymol disrupts bacterial cell membranes and inhibits microbial growth (Hyldgaard *et al.* 2012).

Carvacrol: exhibits potent antibacterial and antifungal activity, especially against foodborne pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Escherichia coli*. It also has anti-inflammatory effects (Burt 2004).

Linalool and borneol: additional terpenoids in thyme oil that contribute to its antimicrobial and soothing properties.

The oil's antioxidant properties are due to the ability of its phenolic compounds to scavenge free radicals and prevent oxidative damage to cells, further enhancing its application in food systems and health products (Brenes and Roura 2010).

Applications in aquaculture and food systems

Thyme essential oil has proven effective as a natural additive in aquaculture. Its antimicrobial properties reduce bacterial infections such as those caused by *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio* species, common in fish farming. Incorporating thyme oil into fish feed boosts immune responses and promotes healthier growth, reducing reliance on synthetic antibiotics (Nazzaro *et al.* 2017; Dawood *et al.* 2022).

In food systems, thyme oil is utilized as a natural preservative due to its ability to inhibit microbial growth and lipid oxidation, thereby extending the shelf life of perishable products. Its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity makes it particularly effective against spoilage organisms and foodborne pathogens (Burt 2004).

Nutritional and functional profile

Thyme essential oil is low in fat but rich in bioactive compounds, particularly thymol and carvacrol. These components are responsible for its strong antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, making the oil a valuable ingredient in functional foods, natural

medicine, and sustainable aquaculture practices (Salehi *et al.* 2018).

→Conehead thyme essential oil

Scientific name: *Thymus capitatus*

Kingdom: Plantae

Order: Lamiales

Family: Lamiaceae

Genus: Thymus

Common name: Conehead thyme

Conehead thyme (*Thymus capitatus*), a species native to Mediterranean regions, is well-regarded for its potent essential oil, characterized by high concentrations of carvacrol and thymol. These compounds exhibit remarkable antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties, making the oil suitable for applications in natural medicine, food preservation, and aquaculture (Brenes and Roura 2010; Salehi *et al.* 2018).

Source and production

The essential oil of conehead thyme is primarily derived from plants cultivated in the Mediterranean basin, particularly in Greece, Turkey, and Spain, where the arid climate and nutrient-rich soils contribute to the synthesis of bioactive compounds. The oil is extracted through steam distillation, a method that ensures the retention of volatile phenolic compounds such as carvacrol and thymol. The Mediterranean climate, with its long growing seasons and abundant sunlight, enhances the plant's bioactive profile, making it a preferred source for high-quality essential oil (Adorjan and Buchbauer 2010).

Bioactive compounds and health benefits

Carvacrol: a monoterpenoid phenol with potent antimicrobial activity, effective against a wide range of pathogens, including *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Listeria monocytogenes*. Carvacrol also exhibits anti-inflammatory properties, reducing oxidative stress and modulating immune responses (Burt 2004).

Thymol: a strong antibacterial and antifungal agent, thymol disrupts microbial cell membranes and inhibits biofilm formation, making it effective in both food preservation and aquaculture applications (Hyltdgaard *et al.* 2012).

Linalool and borneol: terpenes that provide additional antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects, contributing to the oil's therapeutic potential.

These compounds give conehead thyme oil strong antioxidant properties, helping to neutralize free radicals and protect cells from oxidative damage. This makes it suitable for use in functional foods, natural preservatives, and aquaculture systems (Salehi *et al.* 2018).

Applications in aquaculture and food systems

In aquaculture, conehead thyme essential oil serves as a natural alternative to

antibiotics. Its antimicrobial activity reduces bacterial infections caused by pathogens such as *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Vibrio* species, while its antioxidant properties enhance the health and growth performance of fish. By incorporating conehead thyme oil into fish feed, aquaculture practices can become more sustainable, reducing the risk of antibiotic resistance (Nazzaro *et al.* 2017; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

In food preservation, the oil inhibits microbial growth and prevents lipid oxidation, extending the shelf life of perishable products. Its phenolic compounds also contribute to flavor enhancement, making it a valuable additive in the food industry (Burt 2004).

Nutritional and functional profile

Conehead thyme essential oil is rich in phenolic monoterpenes like carvacrol and thymol, which are responsible for its strong antimicrobial and antioxidant effects. Its high bioactive content makes it valuable for applications in functional foods, natural medicine, and sustainable aquaculture practices (Hyldgaard *et al.* 2012; Salehi *et al.* 2018).

3. Recovery of bioactive ingredients from selected plant and algal species through green extraction methods

The selected plants and herbs (sub-chapter 2.2) have been subjected to several extraction protocols, both conventional (Soxhlet extraction) and green (microwave-assisted and ultrasound-assisted, and a combination of both, and pressurized-liquid extraction or their combination) for the recovery of bioactive compounds. Extractions were kinetically studied to be optimized as a function of temperature, extraction time, extraction solvent to biomass ratio, power, and applied solvent. The extraction yields are determined to screen the total extractable potential of the plants.

3.1 Raw material processing

Before proceeding with chemical and biological assessments, each raw material underwent specific preparation steps to preserve its bioactivity and ensure uniformity for the application of various extraction methods. Additionally, chemical assessments were conducted to validate the presence and concentration of key bioactive compounds, ensuring the suitability of the matrices for further testing. Some of the raw materials were sourced from certified suppliers to maintain quality and consistency.

Lemon peel – LP/Orange peel OP Untreated lemons of the Verna variety, sourced from a local market (imported from La Murada, Alicante), were processed through peeling, drying, and grinding in preparation for hydrolysis (Figure 2). The lemons were dried at 40°C for approximately three days to ensure optimal moisture removal. After drying, they were ground using the JustBuy High-Speed Multifunctional Grinder CE (pictured), which operates with a capacity of 800 g, a peak power of 3000 W, and a rotation speed of 36,000 rpm. This stainless-steel grinder produces a particle

size between 50–300 mesh, ensuring a consistent powder suitable for enzyme hydrolysis (pectinase). Same was done for orange peel.

Figure 2. Preparation of lemon peel powder (a – weighting and cleaning; b – peeling; c – drying; d – grinding)

Olive leaves - OL were sourced from Greece and used for the extraction process, highlighting the region's rich tradition in olive cultivation. The leaves underwent a meticulous preparation process before being ground into a fine powder (Figure 3). First, they were carefully washed with distilled water to remove any impurities or residual particles. After washing, the leaves were subjected to air-drying in a controlled environment set at 40°C for a period of 24 hours, ensuring a consistent and gentle drying process that preserved their properties. Once dried, the leaves were ground into a fine powder, which was then passed through a 500 µm sieve to achieve a uniform particle size. This step was crucial for maintaining consistency in subsequent analyses or applications. Finally, the sieved powder was securely stored in a refrigerator, under controlled conditions, to preserve its quality and prevent any degradation until it was ready for use.

Figure 3. Olive leaves preparation

Bog bilberry - In the autumn of 2021, *Vaccinium uliginosum* L. leaves were collected from the wild flora of the 12 Apostles area in Suceava County, Romania. Following harvest, the leaves were dried under controlled conditions in a dark room at ambient temperature for 7–10 days, consistent with methodologies outlined in prior

research (Stefanescu *et al.* 2024). Once dried, the leaves were finely ground into a powder and stored in a cool, dry, and dark environment to preserve their quality until further analysis.

Chlorella and Spirulina - The spirulina and chlorella powders used in this study were provided by Spirulina Supreme (<https://www.spirulina-supreme.gr/>) and BIOIASIS (<https://bioiasisthiva.gr/>), respectively, pre-dried and ground into fine powders. To ensure uniform particle size distribution, the powders were further processed by sieving through a 500 µm sieve. This step helped to eliminate larger agglomerates and ensure consistency in particle size for subsequent applications.

Ulva lactuca - seaweed was acquired from Lusalgae Ltd., located in Figueira da Foz, Portugal. As per the supplier's protocol, the cultivated biomass underwent thorough washing using both filtered and tap water. After removing excess water, the seaweed was dried in a ventilated oven at 60 °C for 48 hours. Subsequently, it was ground using a commercial milling machine and vacuum-sealed to preserve its quality. Upon arrival at the laboratory, the biomass was stored in a controlled environment under dry and dark conditions to prevent exposure to sunlight and maintain its integrity.

Essential oils - of thyme, rosemary, and garlic were procured from Natural Food Additives G.P.C., a reputable supplier specializing in high-quality natural additives. These essential oils were selected for their specific bioactive properties and applications in food and beverage enhancement, ensuring consistency and purity for experimental purposes.

3.2 Extraction of bioactive compounds from selected plants and herbs - conventional and green methods

After the preparation of agricultural by-products (LP, OP, mixture of LP and OP, OL, bog bilberry leaves), herbs (rosemary, thyme, conehead thyme, garlic, eucalyptus), and marine algae (microalgae: spirulina, chlorella, and macroalgae *Ulva lactuca*), the recovery of bioactive substances was carried out through innovative, green extraction technologies (Ultrasound assisted extraction – UAE; Pressurised-liquid extraction (PLE); Ultrasounds-assisted extraction + Microwave-assisted extraction – UAE/MAE; High-pressure extraction (HPE)) together with the Conventional extraction – Soxhlet method, as illustrated in Figure 4.

3.2.1 Conventional extraction method – Soxhlet (S)

The samples were weighed (7.5 g) and transferred into a Soxhlet extractor thimble. Different solvents, water, and ethyl acetate were poured into a conical flask with a capacity of 250 mL. The mixtures were subjected to reflux using a heated mantle for extraction (4 h). Once the designated extraction time had elapsed, the extract solution was permitted to cool down to ambient temperature. A filtration was done before the analysis, through MF-Millipore™ Membrane Filter, 0.45 µm pore size.

3.2.2 Green extraction methods

3.2.2.1 Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE)

During the ultrasound-assisted extraction, the samples were attached to ultrasonic extraction using a 20 kHz Sonicator (Ultrasonics, USA) to 30W power, for 30 min. Energy input was given through a 14×100 mm (diameter length) titanium sonotrode, plunged into the liquid at a predetermined amplitude with an on: off cycle per second. The samples were cooled in an ice bath to reduce the temperature from the ultrasound. A filtration was done before the analysis, through MF-Millipore™ Membrane Filter, 0.45 µm pore size. In Table 2 below are illustrated the different parameters used for Ultrasound Assisted Extraction for microalgae.

Table 2. Parameters used for Ultrasound Assisted Extraction for microalgae

Microalgae	Solvent	Solid to Solvent Ratio	Extraction Time (min)
<i>Spirulina Platensis</i>	Water	1:20	10
	Ethanol	1:20	
	Ethanol/Water 80/20	1:20	
	Ethyl acetate	1:20	
<i>Chlorella Vulgaris</i>	Water	1:20	10
	Ethanol	1:20	
	Ethanol/Water 80/20	1:20	
	Ethyl acetate	1:20	

3.2.2.2 Ultrasound assisted extraction + Microwave assisted extraction (UAE/MAE)

Ultrasound-assisted extraction + Microwave-assisted extraction (UAE/MAE) involved an XO-SM50 Ultrasonic Microwave Reaction System operated at a frequency of 25 kHz, with a power setting of 450 W, and a temperature of 25°C, with the overall extraction duration set at 15 minutes. The solid-to-solvent ratio was 1:20 g dry weight per mL solvent in a beaker while ethyl acetate and water served as the solvents for the extraction. After extraction, a centrifugation (Centrifugator NF400, nuve (Link Lab)) and a filtration steps (MF-Millipore™ Membrane Filters) - pore size of 0.45 µm – were used and afterwards, the samples were stored at -20°C in a freezer.

3.2.2.3 Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE)

PLE system manufactured by Fluid Management Systems Inc (FMS, Waltham, MA, USA) with DMS 6000 software, real-time monitoring of temperature and pressure dynamic adjustments (pump, flow rate, solvent type, extraction duration, valve state, and cooling parameters) involved 5g of dried OL/citrus peels powder loaded into a stainless-steel extraction cell equipped with Teflon end caps and filters and 100 ml volume of solvents (water, ethyl acetate) - maximum operating pressure of 1750 psi. The extraction temperature was 35–38 °C, 15 min extraction time, and after extraction samples were stored at – 20 °C.

3.2.2.4 High-pressure extraction (HPE)

The HPE procedure was conducted following the study of Ben Hamissa *et al.* (Ben Hamissa *et al.* 2012), with slight modifications as follows: a Parr 4790 reactor (PARR Instrument Company, Moline, IL, USA) was used, outfitted with a Controller 4838 and modified with dual valves and pressure regulators to enable the controlled introduction and evacuation of CO₂ and N₂ gases within the reaction chamber. In two steps, 1.5 g of bog bilberry leaf powder was extracted in the static mode for 60 min using 21 mL of 40% v/v ethanol/water as a solvent. In the first stage, the experiment was carried out by replacing air by flushing carbon dioxide through the hermetically closed stainless steel chamber, before increasing and maintaining the pressure at 1000 kPa for 10 min. The second step involved introducing nitrogen until the gas mixture reached a stable pressure of 4000 kPa at 50 °C. After 50 min, the gas mixture was carefully ejected from the reaction chamber, and the extract was separated by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 10 min at 24 °C. The resulting supernatant was stored at a temperature of –18 °C, pending further analyses.

3.2.2.5 Hydro-distillation for herbs

Hydro-distillation uses water (steam) as an extraction solvent to recover volatile or polar components of plant materials. Hydro-distillation is often carried out using a setup known as Clevenger apparatus or simple steam distillation (Figure 4). In the Clevenger apparatus, sample mixed water is boiled to evaporate volatile components while in the steam distillation approach, steam is passed through a bed of the sample. In both approaches, two layers (aqueous and oil-rich) are obtained and oil can be further separated via separating funnels. In this technique, separation of aroma compounds from water, particularly polar ones, is a challenging task and perhaps the greatest limitation of hydro-distillation type extraction.

Figure 4. *Equipment used for types of extractions*

3.2.3 Optimization of extraction methods of bioactive compounds from selected matrices

After analysing results obtained for each matrix and each method applied, several optimization processes were performed. The citrus peels extraction in water implied an optimization step before extraction, they underwent a pretreatment process to remove pectin from the sample (utilizing an enzyme to decrease the pectin content – enzymatic hydrolysis), as illustrated in **Figure 5** below. Pectin posed an issue as it hindered proper filtration of the sample before the subsequent HPLC analysis. This hydrolysis pretreatment step was carried out prior to extraction and post-extraction (in case of PLE water extraction). For water samples, the pretreatment involved lyophilisation of the sample after applying an enzyme to break down pectin. On the other hand, for ethyl acetate samples, evaporation to dryness was employed before further utilization. Optimization of OL extraction - consisted in implementing a maceration step of 4 hours, to better extract the phenolic compounds.

Figure 5. *Citrus peel hydrolysis protocol*

The optimization of phenolic compound extraction from various matrices, as presented in Table 3 below, highlights the tailored approaches required for efficient recovery of bioactive compounds. The table demonstrates that extraction methodologies such as UAE, Soxhlet extraction, and PLE, combined with solvents like water, ethanol, and ethyl acetate, are optimized to maximize phenolic yield and functionality.

Water, as an eco-friendly solvent, effectively extracts hydrophilic phenolics, especially when combined with enzymatic pretreatments like pectinase for citrus peels. Ethanol (80%, 40%) is widely used for its ability to balance hydrophilic and lipophilic phenolic extraction, particularly in olive leaves and citrus matrices. Ethyl acetate excels in recovering lipophilic phenolics and volatile compounds from herbs and algae. Methodological optimizations, such as lyophilization and solvent reconstitution, ensure the stability and concentration of phenolics for downstream applications. HPLC, along with antioxidant (DPPH) and antimicrobial (MIC) assays, validates the biological activities of the extracted compounds.

The table underscores the importance of method customization for each matrix to enhance the recovery of phenolic compounds. By combining appropriate solvents, extraction techniques, and pre/post-extraction treatments, these methods yield compounds with high bioactivity, supporting applications in food, health, and sustainable aquaculture practices. This structured approach to optimization offers a comprehensive pathway for utilizing natural resources effectively while promoting sustainability.

Table 3. Optimization table for extraction of phenolic compounds from different matrices using different methods

Methodology	Solvent	Matrix	Quantity	Obtained results	Optimization
	Ethanol 80%	1. LP - UAE	3 g in 15 mL		
		2. OL - UAE	3 g in 15 mL		4 h maceration
UAE	Water	1. LP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Post extraction method – pectinase, optimization to 1:5 weight to solvent ratio
		2. OP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Post extraction method – pectinase, optimization to 1:5 weight to solvent ratio
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Post extraction method – pectinase, optimization to 1:5 weight to solvent ratio
		4. OL	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, MIC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. OL	1g in 10 mL		4 h maceration
		6. Spirulina			
		7. Chlorella			
	Ethyl acetate	1. LP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, DPPH, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	1 g in 100 mL	HPLC, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. OL	1 g in 10 mL		4 h maceration
		6. Spirulina			
		7. Chlorella			

Soxhlet	Water	1. LP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
	Ethyl acetate	1. LP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	7.5 g in 150 mL	HPLC, MIC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
PLE	Water	1. LP	1 g in 5 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	1 g in 5 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 5 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	20g in 100 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. Spirulina	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Extraction with silica beads
		6. Chlorella	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Extraction with silica beads
	Ethyl acetate	1. LP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness,

					reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	20 g in 100 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. Spirulina	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		6. Chlorella	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
UAE/MAE	Water	1. LP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. Spirulina	2 g in 40 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
		6. Chlorella	2 g in 40 mL	HPLC	Lyophilization, reconstituted in 5 mL
	Ethyl acetate	1. LP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		2. OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		3. Mixed LP + OP	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		4. OL	1 g in 20 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL
		5. Spirulina	2 g in 40 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness,

					reconstituted in 5 mL
		6. Chlorella	2 g in 40 mL	HPLC	Rotaevaporation to dryness, reconstituted in 5 mL

3.3 Characterization of produced extracts

3.3.1 HPLC-DAD-MS-ESI + analysis for identification and quantification of the main compounds of analysed extracts (Agricultural by-products, microalgae)

HPLC-DAD-MS-ESI + analysis of phenolic compounds for agricultural by-product extracts

Sample preparation

The extracts were filtered through nylon filter (pore size 0.45 µm) and 20 µl was injected in HPLC system.

Chromatographic condition

Analysis was carried out using an HP-1200 liquid chromatograph equipped with a quaternary pump, autosampler, DAD detector, and MS-6110 single quadrupole API-electrospray detector (Agilent-Technologies, USA). The positive ionization mode was applied to detect the phenolic compounds; different fragmentor, in the range of 50-100 V, were applied. The column was a Kinetex XB-C18 (5 µm; 4.5x150 mm i.d.) from Phenomenex, USA.

The mobile phase was (A) water acidified by acetic acid 0.1 % and (B) acetonitrile acidified by acetic acid 0.1 %. The following multistep linear gradient was applied: start with 5% B for 2 min; from 5% to 90% of B in 20 min, hold for 4 min at 90% B, then 6 min to arrive at 5% B. Total time of analysis was 30 min, flow rate 0.5 ml/min and oven temperature 25±0.5 °C.

Mass spectrometric detection of positively charged ions was performed using the Scan mode. The applied experimental conditions were gas temperature 3500 C, nitrogen flow 7 l/min, nebulizer pressure 35 psi, capillary voltage 3000 V, fragmentor 100 V, and m/z 120-1500.

Chromatograms were recorded at wavelength $\lambda=280$ nm, and $\lambda=340$ nm, and data acquisition was done with the Agilent ChemStation software, Rev B.02.01-SR2 [260] version.

The flavones content was calculated using a five-point calibration curve of luteolin ($R^2=0.9972$) in the linearity range 1-100 µg/ml.

The flavanones content was calculated using a five-point calibration curve of hesperidin ($R^2=0.9968$) in the linearity range 100-1000 µg/ml.

The tyrosols content was determined using a five-point calibration curve of oleuropein ($R^2=0.9978$) in the linearity range 10-50 µg/ml.

The hydroxybenzoic acid and phenolic terpene content was determined using a five-point calibration curve of gallic acid ($R^2=0.9978$) in the linearity range 10-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The hydroxycinnamic acid content was determined using a five-point calibration curve of chlorogenic acid ($R^2=0.9937$) in the linearity range 10-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Chemical reagents and materials

Acetonitrile, HPLC-gradient, was provided by Merck (Germany) and water was purified with a Direct-Q UV system by Millipore (USA). The pure standard of luteolin and hesperidin (purity 99% HPLC) were purchased from Sigma (USA).

HPLC-DAD analysis for Carotenoids and Chlorophylls in microalgae extracts

Sample Preparation

A 0.1 g sample was mixed with 5 ml of a solvent mixture comprising methanol, petroleum ether, and ethyl acetate in a 1:1:1 (v/v) ratio. The mixture was vortexed for 1 minute, subjected to ultrasonic treatment for 15 minutes at room temperature, and then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The resulting supernatant was collected and stored in a dark place. The extraction process was repeated 4–5 times by re-adding the extraction solvent to the pellet, followed by sonication and centrifugation under the same conditions.

The supernatants from each centrifugation step were combined and transferred to a separating funnel. A saline solution (15% concentration) was added, allowing the aqueous phase to separate and flow out through the tap, leaving the ethereal phase in the funnel. This ethereal phase contained carotenoids and chlorophylls.

The extract was concentrated through evaporation, and the residue was redissolved in 3 ml of ethyl acetate. The solution was then filtered using a nylon filter with a pore size of 0.45 μm . Finally, 20 μl of the prepared extract was injected into the HPLC system.

Chromatographic Conditions

The HPLC analysis of individual carotenoids was performed on an Agilent 1200 system equipped with a DAD detector (Agilent Technologies, USA). A reversed-phase EC 250/4.6 Nucleodur 300-5 C-18 ec column (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm ; Macherey-Nagel, Germany) was used.

The mobile phase consisted of: Solvent A: Acetonitrile: water (9:1, v/v) with 0.25% triethylamine, and Solvent B: Ethyl acetate with 0.25% triethylamine.

The gradient elution began with 90% solvent A at 0 minutes, reducing to 50% A at 10 minutes. It further decreased to 10% A at 20 minutes. The flow rate was maintained at 1 ml/min, and the chromatogram was monitored at wavelengths of 410 nm, 450 nm, and 663 nm. Carotenoid and chlorophyll standards from Sigma (USA) were used for peak identification.

Calibration curves were made using five different concentrations (1–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) of lutein, β -carotene, chlorophyll a and b (purity 99%) from Sigma Company (USA), the

equations of the calibration curves were used to calculate the content of carotenoids and chlorophylls for each sample.

Chemical reagents and materials

Acetonitrile, HPLC-gradient, was provided by Merck (Germany) and water was purified with a Direct-Q UV system by Millipore (USA).

3.3.1.1 HPLC results of citrus matrices

Table 4 presents the quantitative analysis of flavonoids, specifically flavanones and flavones, identified in lemon and orange peel samples using UAE. The results are categorized based on the type of solvent—ethyl acetate and water—and the matrix used, including individual lemon and orange peels, as well as their mixtures. The table includes key phenolic compounds like hesperidin, naringin, and eriocitrin, known for their bioactive properties, offering insights into the impact of solvent choice and matrix composition on flavonoid recovery.

Table 4. The content of flavonoids (flavanone and flavone) in lemon and orange peel samples, **UAE extraction**, expressed in mg/g

Peak Nr.	Phenolic Compound	Lemon ethyl acetate	Orange ethyl acetate	Mix ethyl acetate	Lemon water	Orange water	Mix water
1	Isosakuranetin-neohesperidoside (Poncirin)	0.010	0.016	0.009	5.986	2.533	5.263
2	Isosakuranetin-rutinoside (Didymin)	0.000	0.000	0.000	4.201	4.076	3.550
3	Diosmetin-diglucoside	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.780	0.472	0.694
4	Eriodictyol-rutinoside (Eriocitrin)	0.580	0.000	0.201	32.909	1.203	24.521
5	Diosmetin-glucoside	0.015	0.011	0.012	0.613	0.112	0.518
6	Naringenin-neohesperidoside (Naringin)	0.053	0.110	0.078	0.998	3.925	1.141
7	Diosmetin-rutinoside	0.106	0.018	0.042	0.254	0.097	0.120

(Diosmin)							
8	Hesperetin-rutinoside (Hesperidin)	1.186	0.270	0.442	27.332	9.761	25.226
9	Sinensetin	0.119	0.485	0.240	0.011	0.032	0.013
10	Nobiletin	0.085	0.982	0.538	0.003	0.022	0.010
11	3-Methoxynobiletin	0.017	0.473	0.251	0.004	0.036	0.016
12	Tangeretin	0.021	0.150	0.100	0.016	0.152	0.038
Total flavonoids		2.191	2.514	1.914	73.107	22.420	61.109

TFC in lemon and orange peel samples varied significantly between the solvents (ethyl acetate and water) and the extraction conditions. Water-based extraction exhibited substantially higher flavonoid yields compared to ethyl acetate extraction for both citrus species. For instance, the TFC in LP extracted with water was 73.107 mg/g, compared to only 2.191 mg/g with ethyl acetate. Similarly, OP yielded 22.420 mg/g in water extracts versus 2.514 mg/g in ethyl acetate extracts. These findings are consistent with literature demonstrating the superiority of water in extracting glycosylated flavonoids, such as hesperidin and eriocitrin, due to their high polarity (Guimarães *et al.* 2013; Li, Smith, *et al.* 2006). Moreover, the TPC measured with Folin-Ciocalteu method was 93.011 mg GAE/g.

Water extraction was particularly effective for isolating glycosylated flavonoids, as reflected in the high concentrations of eriodictyol-rutinoside (eriocitrin) and hesperetin-rutinoside (hesperidin). Lemon water extracts contained 32.909 mg/g of eriocitrin, which was almost 60 times higher than in the ethyl acetate extracts (0.580 mg/g). Similarly, hesperidin levels were significantly higher in water extracts for both lemon and orange samples, with lemon water extracts yielding 27.332 mg/g compared to 1.186 mg/g in ethyl acetate extracts. These results align with findings that water excels at extracting polar compounds due to its ability to disrupt hydrogen bonding in plant matrices (Chemat *et al.* 2017).

In contrast, ethyl acetate extraction was more effective for isolating non-polar flavonoids, such as nobiletin, sinensetin, and tangeretin. For instance, nobiletin concentrations in orange ethyl acetate extracts reached 0.982 mg/g, significantly higher than in water extracts (0.022 mg/g). Similarly, sinensetin and tangeretin showed higher yields in ethyl acetate extracts. This trend is consistent with the literature, which indicates that less polar solvents like ethyl acetate are better suited for extracting lipophilic and methoxylated flavonoids (Xu *et al.* 2007; Ghasemzadeh and Jaafar 2011).

Some flavonoids exhibited unique distributions based on species and solvent. For example, isosakuranetin-neohesperidoside (poncirin) was highly abundant in lemon water extracts (5.986 mg/g) but was either absent or present in trace amounts in ethyl acetate extracts. Similarly, naringenin-neohesperidoside (naringin) was much more concentrated in orange water extracts (3.925 mg/g) compared to other conditions. These variations highlight species-specific flavonoid profiles and the role of solvent polarity in extraction efficiency (Durmus *et al.* 2024).

The flavonoid profiles differed significantly between lemon and orange peels. LP demonstrated higher concentrations of polar flavonoids like eriocitrin and hesperidin in water extracts. For example, lemon water extracts yielded 32.909 mg/g of eriocitrin compared to only 1.203 mg/g in orange water extracts. Conversely, OP was richer in methoxylated flavonoids, such as nobiletin and sinensetin, particularly in ethyl acetate extracts. These findings align with prior studies suggesting that OP contain higher levels of lipophilic flavonoids, while LP are more abundant in hydrophilic compounds (Guimarães *et al.* 2013; Xu *et al.* 2007).

The use of UAE significantly enhanced the yield of flavonoids compared to conventional methods like Soxhlet extraction, as reported in similar studies (Chemat *et al.* 2017). UAE improves the extraction process by disrupting plant cell walls and enhancing solvent penetration, resulting in higher recovery of bioactive compounds. This efficiency is evident in the markedly high yields of glycosylated flavonoids such as eriocitrin and hesperidin in water-based UAE, making it a preferred method for these compounds.

The results demonstrate that solvent selection plays a critical role in determining the composition and yield of extracted flavonoids. Water is optimal for polar, glycosylated flavonoids, which have applications in nutraceuticals and functional foods due to their high AA. Ethyl acetate, on the other hand, is better suited for extracting non-polar, methoxylated flavonoids, which are valuable for their anti-inflammatory and anticancer properties (Durmus *et al.* 2024; Xu *et al.* 2007). These findings provide a basis for tailoring solvent and extraction methods to target specific flavonoid profiles.

The analysis of flavonoid content extracted from lemon and orange peels using Soxhlet extraction revealed a clear influence of solvent type on the yield and composition of flavonoids, as displayed in Table 5.

Table 5. The content of flavonoids (flavanone and flavone) in lemon and orange peel samples, Soxhlet extraction, expressed in mg/g

Peak Nr.	Phenolic Compound	Lemon ethyl acetate	Orange ethyl acetate	Mix ethyl acetate	Lemon water	Orange water	Mix water
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Table 5. The content of flavonoids (flavanone and flavone) in lemon and orange peel samples, Soxhlet extraction, expressed in mg/g

1	Isosakuranetin -neohesperidoside (Poncirin)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.032	0.000	0.021
2	Isosakuranetin -rutinoside (Didymin)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.039	0.000	0.000
3	Diosmetin- diglucoside	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.021	0.003	0.017
4	Eriodictyol- rutinoside (Eriocitrin)	0.055	0.000	0.021	0.671	0.014	0.633
5	Diosmetin- glucoside	0.003	0.022	0.015	0.007	0.002	0.001
6	Naringenin- neohesperidoside (Naringin)	0.000	0.010	0.000	0.000	0.087	0.000
7	Diosmetin- rutinoside (Diosmin)	0.046	0.048	0.042	0.007	0.002	0.004
8	Hesperetin- rutinoside (Hesperidin)	0.294	0.316	0.244	0.574	0.292	0.553
9	Sinensetin	0.099	0.399	0.312	0.000	0.000	0.000
10	Nobiletin	0.221	0.763	0.551	0.000	0.000	0.000
11	3-Methoxynobiletin	0.082	0.343	0.211	0.000	0.000	0.000
12	Tangeretin	0.033	0.100	0.073	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Total flavonoids	0.833	2.000	1.470	1.351	0.401	1.230

Ethyl acetate extracts demonstrated higher flavonoid content in OP (2.000 mg/g) compared to LP (0.833 mg/g) and mixed samples (1.470 mg/g). Conversely, water extracts exhibited higher flavonoid content in LP (1.351 mg/g) compared to OP (0.401 mg/g). These findings suggest that ethyl acetate is particularly effective for extracting lipophilic flavonoids, while water is more suitable for extracting hydrophilic compounds. Similar patterns have been reported in the literature, where solvent

polarity is shown to significantly influence the type and yield of extracted flavonoids (Chemat *et al.* 2017; Ghasemzadeh and Jaafar 2011).

Water was the preferred solvent for isolating glycosylated flavonoids such as eriocitrin, hesperidin, and poncirin. LP yielded the highest concentration of eriocitrin in water extracts (0.671 mg/g), significantly outperforming the ethyl acetate extract (0.055 mg/g). Hesperidin was another dominant compound in water extracts, with concentrations of 0.574 mg/g in LP and 0.292 mg/g in OP. In comparison, hesperidin concentrations in ethyl acetate extracts were 0.294 mg/g for LP and 0.316 mg/g for OP. Poncirin and didymin were exclusively detected in water extracts, with LP containing 0.032 mg/g and 0.039 mg/g, respectively. The prevalence of glycosylated flavonoids in water extracts is consistent with their hydrophilic nature, as these compounds possess sugar moieties that enhance solubility in polar solvents (Guimarães *et al.* 2013). These findings align with previous studies reporting the efficiency of water in extracting glycosylated flavonoids from citrus peels, particularly in lemon (Xu *et al.* 2007; Durmus *et al.* 2024).

Ethyl acetate extracts were more effective at isolating methoxylated flavonoids, including nobiletin, sinensetin, and tangeretin. OP contained the highest levels of nobiletin in ethyl acetate extracts (0.763 mg/g), followed by mixed samples (0.551 mg/g) and LP (0.221 mg/g). In contrast, water extracts showed no detectable nobiletin. Similarly, sinensetin levels were highest in orange ethyl acetate extracts (0.399 mg/g), while lemon ethyl acetate extracts contained 0.099 mg/g, and water extracts contained none. Tangeretin, another methoxylated flavonoid, followed the same pattern, being more concentrated in orange ethyl acetate extracts (0.100 mg/g) compared to lemon (0.033 mg/g) and mixed extracts (0.073 mg/g). These results are in line with existing literature, which highlights the affinity of semi-polar solvents such as ethyl acetate for lipophilic flavonoids (Ghasemzadeh and Jaafar 2011). Furthermore, the naturally higher abundance of methoxylated flavonoids in OP compared to LP has been well-documented (Li, Lo, *et al.* 2006; González-Molina *et al.* 2010).

The differences in flavonoid composition between lemon and orange peels were evident across both solvents. LP exhibited higher concentrations of glycosylated flavonoids, such as eriocitrin and hesperidin, particularly in water extracts. On the other hand, OP contained significantly higher levels of methoxylated flavonoids, such as nobiletin and sinensetin, especially in ethyl acetate extracts. This observation is consistent with prior studies showing that LP are naturally richer in hydrophilic flavonoids, while OP are a major source of methoxylated flavones (Xu *et al.* 2007; Durmus *et al.* 2024). Mixed samples showed intermediate flavonoid profiles, reflecting the additive or complementary nature of combining both citrus species.

Soxhlet extraction was effective in isolating both polar and non-polar flavonoids when paired with the appropriate solvent. Water proved particularly effective for glycosylated flavonoids due to its polarity, while ethyl acetate efficiently extracted

methoxylated flavonoids. However, the high temperatures associated with Soxhlet extraction may have contributed to the degradation of thermolabile flavonoids, which could explain the absence or lower concentrations of some compounds in certain extracts. These limitations have been highlighted in previous research, where alternative methods such as ultrasound-assisted extraction or PLE have been shown to better preserve thermosensitive bioactive compounds (Chemat *et al.* 2017). Despite this, Soxhlet remains a robust method for flavonoid profiling when targeting specific compound classes.

The higher concentrations of methoxylated flavonoids in orange ethyl acetate extracts align with findings by Li *et al.* (2006)(Li, Lo, *et al.* 2006), who reported similar trends in OP and their preference for non-polar solvents. Similarly, the high levels of glycosylated flavonoids in lemon water extracts corroborate the work of González-Molina *et al.* (2010) (González-Molina *et al.* 2010), who noted the abundance of hydrophilic flavonoids in LP. The efficiency of Soxhlet extraction, while established in this study, has been shown to be less advantageous for thermolabile compounds compared to modern extraction methods like ultrasound-assisted extraction, as discussed by Chemat *et al.* (2017).

The flavonoid content of lemon and orange peel samples extracted using PLE and UAE/MAE demonstrated significant variations influenced by the extraction method, solvent type, and citrus species (Table 6).

Table 6. The content of flavonoids (flavanone and flavone) in lemon and orange peel samples, PLE and UAE/MAE extraction, expressed in mg/g

Peak Nr.	Phenolic Compound	Lemon EA PLE	Orange EA PLE	Mix EA PLE	Lemon EA UAE/MAE	Orange EA UAE/MAE	Mix EA UAE/MAE	Lemon water UAE/MAE	Orange Water UAE/MAE	Mix Water UAE/MAE
1	Isosakurane tin-neohesperid oside (Poncirin)	0.000	0.196	0.087	0.000	0.244	0.017	5.820	2.916	2.522
2	Isosakurane tin-rutinoside (Didymin)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	3.305	1.975	2.031
3	Diosmetin-diglucoside	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.606	0.202	0.450

4	Eriodictyol- rutinoside (Eriocitrin)	0.144	0.000	0.130	0.000	0.000	0.000	24.492	8.013	19.09 5
5	Diosmetin- glucoside	0.004	0.016	0.029	0.000	0.015	0.010	0.388	0.354	0.358
6	Naringenin- neohesperid oside(Naring in)	0.362	0.157	0.051	0.139	0.067	0.084	6.412	6.250	0.928
7	Diosmetin- rutinoside(Di osmin)	0.006	0.000	0.003	0.004	0.000	0.000	0.051	0.000	0.075
8	Hesperetin- rutinoside (Hesperidin)	0.599	0.203	0.312	0.346	0.185	0.351	24.281	10.676	11.40 4
9	Sinensetin	0.080	0.643	0.394	0.082	0.617	0.253	0.525	0.265	0.020
10	Nobiletin	0.022	0.972	0.593	0.032	1.114	0.495	0.101	0.044	0.000
11	3Methoxyno biletin	0.012	0.358	0.219	0.010	0.472	0.224	0.539	0.210	0.001
12	Tangeretin	0.003	0.127	0.080	0.000	0.163	0.076	0.141	0.053	0.001
	Total flavonoids	1.233	2.671	1.898	0.612	2.878	1.512	66.663	30.958	36.88 5

For PLE with ethyl acetate, OP yielded the highest TFC (2.671 mg/g), followed by mixed samples (1.898 mg/g) and LP (1.233 mg/g). In contrast, UAE/MAE with water dramatically increased flavonoid yields, especially for LP, with a TFC of 66.663 mg/g. OP extracted with water UAE/MAE yielded 30.958 mg/g, while mixed samples contained 36.885 mg/g. These results underscore the superior efficiency of UAE/MAE with water for flavonoid extraction, particularly for LP. The enhanced performance of UAE/MAE can be attributed to the mechanical effects of ultrasound and microwave energy, which disrupt plant cell walls and improve solvent penetration and mass transfer, consistent with findings from Chemat *et al.* (2017) and Khan *et al.* (2010) (Chemat *et al.* 2017; Khan *et al.* 2010).

Water UAE/MAE extracts contained significantly higher concentrations of glycosylated flavonoids, including eriocitrin, hesperidin, poncirin, and didymin, compared to ethyl acetate extracts from both PLE and UAE/MAE. Eriocitrin was the most abundant glycosylated flavonoid, particularly in LP extracted with water UAE/MAE (24.492 mg/g). Mixed samples and OP also exhibited high levels of

eriocitrin in water UAE/MAE extracts, with concentrations of 19.095 mg/g and 8.013 mg/g, respectively. Ethyl acetate extracts, regardless of the method used, contained negligible amounts of eriocitrin, highlighting the inefficiency of this solvent for hydrophilic compounds. Similarly, hesperidin showed higher concentrations in water UAE/MAE extracts, with LP yielding 24.281 mg/g, OP 10.676 mg/g, and mixed samples 11.404 mg/g. These values were substantially greater than those observed in ethyl acetate extracts, where LP extracted with PLE and UAE/MAE yielded 0.599 mg/g and 0.346 mg/g, respectively. Poncirin exhibited a similar pattern, with water UAE/MAE extracts containing 5.820 mg/g in LP and 2.916 mg/g in OP, while it was almost absent in ethyl acetate extracts. Didymin, another glycosylated flavonoid, was also predominantly found in water UAE/MAE extracts, with LP containing 3.305 mg/g and OP 1.975 mg/g. The abundance of these glycosylated flavonoids in water extracts aligns with their hydrophilic nature, as their sugar moieties enhance solubility in polar solvents (Guimarães *et al.* 2013). These findings corroborate previous studies that have identified water as a highly effective solvent for extracting glycosylated flavonoids from citrus peels, particularly when assisted by UAE or MAE (González-Molina *et al.* 2010). Methoxylated flavonoids, such as nobiletin, sinensetin, and tangeretin, were more abundant in ethyl acetate extracts, particularly in OP, regardless of the extraction method. Nobiletin was the most prominent methoxylated flavonoid in orange ethyl acetate UAE/MAE extracts (1.114 mg/g), followed by PLE extracts (0.972 mg/g). LP contained significantly lower amounts of nobiletin in ethyl acetate extracts, with UAE/MAE yielding 0.032 mg/g and PLE yielding 0.022 mg/g. In water UAE/MAE extracts, nobiletin was nearly undetectable. Sinensetin exhibited a similar trend, with orange ethyl acetate UAE/MAE extracts yielding 0.617 mg/g compared to 0.643 mg/g in PLE. LP contained minimal amounts of sinensetin in ethyl acetate extracts (0.080 mg/g in PLE and 0.082 mg/g in UAE/MAE), while water extracts contained negligible quantities. Tangeretin concentrations followed the same pattern, with higher levels in orange ethyl acetate UAE/MAE extracts (0.163 mg/g) and PLE extracts (0.127 mg/g) compared to LP, which contained 0.000 mg/g in UAE/MAE extracts. The preferential extraction of methoxylated flavonoids in ethyl acetate reflects their lipophilic nature, making them more soluble in semi-polar solvents (Li, Lo, *et al.* 2006). The higher concentrations of these compounds in OP compared to LP are consistent with their natural abundance in OP, as reported by Xu *et al.* (2007) (Xu *et al.* 2007).

UAE/MAE demonstrated significantly higher efficiency for extracting hydrophilic flavonoids compared to PLE, particularly when using water as the solvent. LP extracted with water UAE/MAE yielded 66.663 mg/g of total flavonoids, far exceeding the 1.233 mg/g obtained with ethyl acetate PLE. This difference underscores the role of advanced extraction techniques in enhancing the recovery of flavonoids. UAE/MAE is particularly effective due to the combined mechanical and thermal effects of ultrasound and microwaves, which facilitate cell disruption and improve solvent

penetration (Chemat *et al.* 2017; Khan *et al.* 2010). For methoxylated flavonoids, PLE and UAE/MAE with ethyl acetate produced comparable yields, with OP consistently showing higher concentrations of compounds like nobiletin and sinensetin.

The flavonoid profiles of lemon and orange peels differed markedly, reflecting inherent compositional variations between the two species. LP contained significantly higher concentrations of hydrophilic flavonoids, such as eriocitrin and hesperidin, especially in water UAE/MAE extracts. In contrast, OP exhibited higher levels of methoxylated flavonoids, such as nobiletin and sinensetin, particularly in ethyl acetate extracts. Mixed samples displayed intermediate flavonoid profiles, indicating the additive effect of combining lemon and orange peels. These differences are consistent with previous studies, which have identified LP as a richer source of hydrophilic flavonoids and OP as a major source of lipophilic flavonoids (González-Molina *et al.* 2010; Xu *et al.* 2007).

The TFC of LP extracted using ultrasound extraction with 80% ethanol was 40.208 mg/g (Table 7). This demonstrates the effectiveness of ethanol as a solvent for extracting a wide range of flavonoids from citrus peels. Ethanol is known for its amphiphilic properties, which allow it to dissolve both polar and non-polar compounds. In this study, its use in ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) enhanced the recovery of flavonoids by facilitating the disruption of cell walls, improving solvent penetration, and increasing the mass transfer of bioactive compounds. These results align with previous research highlighting the efficiency of ethanol-based solvents in UAE for citrus flavonoids (Chemat *et al.* 2017; Khan *et al.* 2010)

Table 7. The content of flavonoids (flavanone and flavone) in lemon peel samples, UAE, expressed in mg/g

Peak Nr.	Phenolic Compound	Lemon Ethanol 80%
1	Isosakuranetin-neohesperidoside (Poncirin)	1.949
2	Isosakuranetin-rutinoside (Didymin)	0.654
3	Diosmetin-diglucoside	0.253
4	Eriodictyol-rutinoside (Eriocitrin)	20.312
5	Diosmetin-glucoside	0.562
6	Naringenin-neohesperidoside (Naringin)	1.781
7	Diosmetin-rutinoside (Diosmin)	0.346
8	Hesperetin-rutinoside (Hesperidin)	14.083
9	Sinensetin	0.179
10	Nobiletin	0.047
11	3-Methoxynobiletin	0.017
12	Tangeretin	0.025
Total flavonoids		40.208

The extraction yielded significant amounts of glycosylated flavonoids, particularly eriocitrin (20.312 mg/g), hesperidin (14.083 mg/g), and poncirin (1.949 mg/g). Eriocitrin, the most abundant flavonoid extracted, is a highly hydrophilic compound due to its glycosylated structure. Its high concentration suggests that ethanol, with its moderate polarity, was effective in extracting such hydrophilic flavonoids while benefiting from the enhanced penetration provided by ultrasound waves. Similarly, hesperidin, another glycosylated flavonoid, exhibited substantial yields, consistent with its natural abundance in citrus peels (González-Molina *et al.* 2010).

The presence of glycosylated flavonoids like poncirin (1.949 mg/g) and didymin (0.654 mg/g) further supports ethanol's ability to solubilize polar flavonoid derivatives. These compounds, which contain sugar moieties, are known to be more soluble in polar solvents. The efficiency of ethanol in extracting these compounds aligns with findings from Guimarães *et al.* (2013), who emphasized the importance of solvent polarity in the recovery of hydrophilic flavonoids from citrus matrices (Guimarães *et al.* 2013).

In contrast to glycosylated flavonoids, methoxylated flavonoids such as nobiletin (0.047 mg/g), sinensetin (0.179 mg/g), and tangeretin (0.025 mg/g) were extracted in much lower quantities. Methoxylated flavonoids are more lipophilic and generally require less polar solvents, such as ethyl acetate, for optimal extraction. The low yields of these compounds in the ethanol extract suggest that while ethanol is versatile, it may not be the ideal solvent for isolating lipophilic flavonoids. This is consistent with earlier studies that have demonstrated higher extraction efficiencies of methoxylated flavonoids in semi-polar solvents (Li, Lo, *et al.* 2006; Xu *et al.* 2007).

The flavonoid profile obtained in this study highlights the dominance of hydrophilic compounds such as eriocitrin and hesperidin in LP. Eriocitrin, which was the most abundant flavonoid, has been recognized for its strong antioxidant properties and potential health benefits. Its high concentration in ethanol extracts demonstrates the suitability of this solvent for targeting health-promoting compounds in citrus peels. Similarly, hesperidin, widely studied for its anti-inflammatory and cardiovascular benefits, was present in substantial amounts, further underscoring the nutritional value of LP extracts (González-Molina *et al.* 2010).

In contrast, the methoxylated flavonoids nobiletin, sinensetin, and tangeretin, which are associated with anticancer and anti-inflammatory properties, were present in much lower concentrations. This result is consistent with the compositional differences between lemon and other citrus species, such as oranges, which are typically richer in methoxylated flavones (Li, Lo, *et al.* 2006).

The use of ultrasound-assisted extraction contributed significantly to the efficient recovery of flavonoids. Ultrasound disrupts plant cell walls, allowing for better

penetration of the solvent into the cellular matrix and enhanced release of bioactive compounds. The high TFC (40.208 mg/g) demonstrates the synergistic effect of ultrasound with ethanol in maximizing flavonoid recovery. This finding is consistent with prior studies, which have reported that UAE improves the yield of flavonoids and other phenolic compounds compared to CE methods (Khan *et al.* 2010; Chemat *et al.* 2017).

The flavonoid composition reported in this study aligns with previous research on citrus peel extractions. Eriocitrin and hesperidin have consistently been identified as the predominant flavonoids in LP, with their high levels reflecting their natural abundance (González-Molina *et al.* 2010; Guimarães *et al.* 2013). The relatively low concentrations of methoxylated flavonoids are also consistent with earlier findings, which attribute their limited presence in LP to species-specific differences in flavonoid composition (Xu *et al.* 2007). Furthermore, the effectiveness of UAE in enhancing flavonoid extraction corroborates findings from (Chemat *et al.* 2017), who highlighted the method's advantages in terms of efficiency and sustainability.

3.3.1.2 HPLC results of olive leaves

Table 8 provides the DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionization of OL samples, showcasing the phenolic compounds quantified in these samples. The table categorizes the compounds by subclass, such as hydroxybenzoic acids, tyrosols, flavones, flavonols, and hydroxycinnamic acids. It further details the concentrations of these phenolics in extracts obtained using UAE and MAE with two different solvents—water and ethyl acetate. This analysis highlights the diversity and quantity of phenolic compounds, which are expressed in mg/g of the sample, offering valuable insights into the phenolic profile of olive leaves.

Table 8. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of phenolic compounds, expressed in mg/g sample (UAE/MAE)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	Extract H ₂ O UAE/MAE	Extract EA UAE/MAE
1	Hydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.725	0.000
2	Dihydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.160	0.000
3	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	0.205	0.000
4	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	0.143	0.000
5	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	0.108	0.000
6	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	0.390	0.035
7	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	0.353	0.031
8	Luteolin-diglucoside	Flavone	0.080	0.001
9	Oleacein	Tyrosol	0.185	0.044

10	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	Flavonol	0.119	0.055
11	Verbascoside	Hydroxycinnamic acid	0.095	0.176
12	Luteolin-glucoside	Flavone	0.095	0.028
13	Apigenin-rutinoside	Flavone	0.034	0.000
14	Apigenin-glucoside	Flavone	0.012	0.029
15	Luteolin-glucuronide	Flavone	0.016	0.013
16	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	0.890	3.446
17	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	0.898	1.037
Total phenolics			4.508	4.894

The analysis of phenolic compounds extracted from OL using UAE/MAE reveals notable differences in the TPC based on the solvent used. Water extracts yielded a TPC of 4.508 mg/g, while ethyl acetate extracts yielded slightly higher levels at 4.894 mg/g. This difference reflects the solubility characteristics of specific phenolic subclasses in the respective solvents. Water, a polar solvent, was particularly effective for extracting polar compounds such as hydroxybenzoic acids, hydroxytyrosol derivatives, and flavones. Ethyl acetate, being semi-polar, was more efficient in extracting less polar compounds, such as oleuropein and its derivatives. Similar observations have been reported in studies on OL, where solvent polarity significantly influenced phenolic recovery (Obied *et al.* 2007; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

Hydroxybenzoic acids, including hydroxybenzoic acid (0.725 mg/g) and dihydroxybenzoic acid (0.160 mg/g), were exclusively extracted in water. These compounds are highly polar, which explains their absence in ethyl acetate extracts. Hydroxybenzoic acids are known for their antioxidant properties, and their abundance in water extracts highlights water's efficacy in extracting highly polar phenolics. These findings align with previous research emphasizing the suitability of water for recovering hydroxybenzoic acids from plant matrices (De Marco *et al.* 2007).

The tyrosol subclass exhibited variability in solubility between the two solvents. Compounds such as hydroxytyrosol-glucoside (0.205 mg/g), hydroxytyrosol (0.143 mg/g), and ligstroside (0.108 mg/g) were exclusively detected in water extracts, reflecting their hydrophilic nature. In contrast, more lipophilic derivatives like oleuropein and oleuropein-aglycone were found in higher concentrations in ethyl acetate extracts. Oleuropein, a key bioactive compound in OL, was present at 3.446 mg/g in ethyl acetate extracts, compared to 0.890 mg/g in water extracts. Similarly, oleuropein-aglycone was more concentrated in ethyl acetate extracts (1.037 mg/g) than in water (0.898 mg/g). The preference of these compounds for ethyl acetate aligns with their semi-polar nature and highlights the solvent's efficiency in extracting oleuropein and its derivatives (Obied *et al.* 2007).

Flavonoids, including flavones and flavonols, showed varying extraction efficiencies between water and ethyl acetate. Luteolin-diglucoside (0.080 mg/g), quercetin-rutinoside (rutin) (0.119 mg/g), and apigenin-rutinoside (0.034 mg/g) were predominantly found in water extracts, while their concentrations were significantly lower in ethyl acetate extracts. Conversely, some flavonoids, such as apigenin-glucoside (0.029 mg/g) and luteolin-glucoside (0.028 mg/g), were more efficiently extracted with ethyl acetate, although their overall concentrations were low. These results suggest that the choice of solvent significantly affects flavonoid recovery, with water being more effective for highly polar glycosylated flavonoids and ethyl acetate favoring less polar derivatives. This is consistent with earlier studies, which highlight the impact of solvent polarity on the solubility of flavonoids (Ghanbari *et al.* 2012). Verbascoside, a hydroxycinnamic acid derivative, was the only compound from this subclass that exhibited a higher concentration in ethyl acetate extracts (0.176 mg/g) compared to water extracts (0.095 mg/g). Verbascoside is moderately polar, and its affinity for ethyl acetate reflects its intermediate solubility characteristics. These findings are consistent with the literature, which reports that hydroxycinnamic acids can be extracted efficiently with both polar and semi-polar solvents depending on their degree of glycosylation (De Marco *et al.* 2007).

The differences in the extraction profiles between water and ethyl acetate highlight the importance of solvent polarity in phenolic compound recovery. Water, being highly polar, was more effective in extracting hydrophilic compounds such as hydroxybenzoic acids, hydroxytyrosol derivatives, and glycosylated flavonoids. In contrast, ethyl acetate was more efficient in recovering less polar compounds, such as oleuropein, oleuropein-aglycone, and verbascoside. These results corroborate findings from previous studies that emphasize the role of solvent selection in optimizing the extraction of specific phenolic subclasses from OL (Obied *et al.* 2007; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

The phenolic composition of OL observed in this study aligns with previous research on the phenolic profiles of OL. The high levels of oleuropein and oleuropein-aglycone in ethyl acetate extracts are consistent with their reported abundance in OL and their semi-polar nature (Obied *et al.* 2007). Similarly, the prevalence of hydroxytyrosol derivatives in water extracts is in agreement with studies highlighting the hydrophilic properties of these compounds (De Marco *et al.* 2007). The observed differences in flavonoid recovery between water and ethyl acetate also align with findings that demonstrate the varying solubility of flavonoid glycosides and aglycones in polar and semi-polar solvents, respectively (Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

The total tyrosol content of olive leaf extracts obtained through UAE/MAE differed significantly between water and ethyl acetate solvents (Table 9).

Table 9. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of tyrosols, expressed in mg/g sample (**UAE/MAE**)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	Extract H ₂ O UAE/MAE	Extract EA UAE/MAE
1	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	0.205	0.000
2	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	0.143	0.000
3	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	0.108	0.000
4	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	0.390	0.035
5	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	0.353	0.031
6	Oleacein	Tyrosol	0.185	0.044
7	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	0.890	3.446
8	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	0.898	1.037
Total tyrosols			3.172	4.593

Ethyl acetate extracts exhibited higher total tyrosol content (4.593 mg/g) compared to water extracts (3.172 mg/g). This indicates the greater suitability of ethyl acetate for recovering semi-polar tyrosol derivatives, while water demonstrated efficiency in extracting hydrophilic tyrosols. The polarity of the solvent played a critical role in shaping the extraction profile, confirming the selective solubility of these phenolics based on their structural properties (Obied *et al.* 2007; De Marco *et al.* 2007).

The hydrophilic tyrosol derivatives, such as hydroxytyrosol-glucoside, hydroxytyrosol, and ligstroside, were exclusively recovered in water extracts, with concentrations of 0.205 mg/g, 0.143 mg/g, and 0.108 mg/g, respectively. These findings further demonstrate the affinity of polar compounds for water extraction. Meanwhile, semi-polar tyrosols such as oleuropein and oleuropein-aglycone were substantially more concentrated in ethyl acetate extracts, with oleuropein reaching 3.446 mg/g compared to 0.890 mg/g in water. Oleuropein-aglycone also followed this trend, with 1.037 mg/g in ethyl acetate extracts versus 0.898 mg/g in water.

The extraction profile of oleacein, an oxidized derivative of oleuropein, showed moderate levels in both solvents, with a slight preference for ethyl acetate (0.044 mg/g) over water (0.185 mg/g). This highlights the intermediate solubility of some phenolics, which exhibit dual affinity for both polar and semi-polar solvents (Ghanbari *et al.* 2012). The differential solubility of tyrosol derivatives between water and ethyl acetate emphasizes the solvent-dependent extraction behavior. Water consistently extracted smaller molecular weight tyrosols with free hydroxyl groups, reflecting its effectiveness for hydrophilic compounds. In contrast, ethyl acetate selectively enriched the extracts with high molecular weight tyrosol derivatives, including glycosylated and esterified forms, which possess semi-polar properties. This selective behavior is advantageous

for tailoring extraction processes to specific applications, such as maximizing antioxidant tyrosols for pharmaceutical or nutraceutical formulations (De Marco *et al.* 2007; Obied *et al.* 2007).

Oleuropein, the most abundant tyrosol derivative in ethyl acetate extracts, is known for its diverse bioactivities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Its high concentration in ethyl acetate extracts underscores the potential for utilizing semi-polar solvents to maximize the recovery of bioactive compounds. Meanwhile, the significant presence of hydroxytyrosol and hydroxytyrosol-glucoside in water extracts highlights their suitability for antioxidant applications due to their higher radical-scavenging efficiency compared to esterified derivatives (Ghanbari *et al.* 2012; Obied *et al.* 2007).

The patterns observed in this study align with previous research on OL. The efficient recovery of oleuropein and its aglycone in ethyl acetate has been widely documented, highlighting its semi-polar nature and the solvent's compatibility. Similarly, hydroxytyrosol and its derivatives, which are abundant in water extracts, have been consistently reported as key phenolics contributing to the antioxidant potential of OL. These findings support the well-documented relationship between solvent polarity and the phenolic profile of olive leaf extracts (De Marco *et al.* 2007; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

TPC of olive leaf extracts obtained using Soxhlet and UAE was comparable across both methods, with values ranging from 34.787 mg/g to 36.232 mg/g (Table 10).

Table 10. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of phenolic compounds, expressed in mg/g sample (**UAE and Soxhlet extraction**)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	Soxhlet Water	Soxhlet EA	UAE Water	UAE EA
1	Hydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.717	0.000	0.456	0.000
2	Dihydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	4.081	0.000	1.937	0.000
3	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	1.791	0.000	1.244	0.000
4	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	4.528	0.000	1.649	0.000
5	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	1.493	0.000	1.213	0.000
6	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	1.240	0.000	1.991	0.000
7	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	2.245	0.087	2.053	0.187

Table 10. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of phenolic compounds, expressed in mg/g sample (**UAE and Soxhlet extraction**)

8	Luteolin-diglucoside	Flavone	0.510	0.028	0.617	0.003
9	Oleacein	Tyrosol	1.443	1.638	1.244	1.452
10	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	Flavonol	0.654	0.180	1.080	0.281
11	Verbascoside	Hydroxycinnamic acid	0.793	1.170	1.004	1.469
12	Luteolin-glucoside	Flavone	1.512	0.574	1.830	0.331
13	Apigenin-rutinoside	Flavone	0.351	0.059	0.643	0.539
14	Apigenin-glucoside	Flavone	0.719	0.864	1.358	0.250
15	Luteolin-glucuronide	Flavone	0.346	0.857	0.842	0.677
16	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	9.315	24.653	12.025	24.589
17	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	3.048	6.120	3.763	6.054
Total phenolics			34.787	36.232	34.950	35.831

Soxhlet extraction with ethyl acetate yielded the highest total phenolics (36.232 mg/g), closely followed by UAE with ethyl acetate (35.831 mg/g). Water extracts from both methods also demonstrated high total phenolic recovery, with Soxhlet water extracts yielding 34.787 mg/g and UAE water extracts yielding 34.950 mg/g. These results suggest that both extraction techniques are effective for recovering phenolic compounds, with minor variations attributable to solvent polarity and the thermal or mechanical mechanisms involved in the extraction process. Previous studies have also reported similar phenolic yields between Soxhlet and UAE, with UAE showing an advantage in preserving thermosensitive compounds due to its lower operating temperatures (Chemat *et al.* 2017; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012).

Water extracts consistently showed higher concentrations of polar phenolics, while ethyl acetate extracts were more efficient for semi-polar compounds. For instance, highly polar compounds such as hydroxybenzoic acid (0.717 mg/g) and dihydroxybenzoic acid (4.081 mg/g) were present exclusively in water extracts. In contrast, semi-polar compounds such as oleuropein and oleuropein-aglycone were substantially more concentrated in ethyl acetate extracts. Soxhlet ethyl acetate extracts yielded the highest concentrations of oleuropein (24.653 mg/g) and oleuropein-aglycone (6.120 mg/g), slightly exceeding UAE ethyl acetate extracts. These findings align with previous research emphasizing the role of solvent polarity in

determining the solubility and recovery of specific phenolic subclasses (Obied *et al.* 2007; De Marco *et al.* 2007).

Soxhlet extraction exhibited a slight advantage over UAE in recovering certain compounds, particularly those requiring prolonged solvent interaction, such as oleuropein and oleuropein-aglycone. However, UAE showed superior efficiency for extracting thermosensitive flavonoids and hydrophilic phenolics, likely due to its lower operating temperatures and enhanced cell wall disruption via ultrasonic cavitation. For example, quercetin-rutinoside (rutin) showed higher concentrations in UAE water extracts (1.080 mg/g) compared to Soxhlet water extracts (0.654 mg/g), reflecting UAE's ability to preserve flavonoids that are susceptible to thermal degradation (Chemat *et al.* 2017). Similarly, UAE water extracts showed slightly higher levels of luteolin-diglucoside (0.617 mg/g) compared to Soxhlet water extracts (0.510 mg/g).

Tyrosol derivatives, including oleuropein, oleuropein-aglycone, and oleoside dimethylester, were more efficiently extracted using ethyl acetate in both methods. Oleuropein and its aglycone were the dominant compounds across all extracts, with the highest concentrations observed in ethyl acetate extracts. Soxhlet ethyl acetate extracts yielded 24.653 mg/g of oleuropein and 6.120 mg/g of its aglycone, while UAE ethyl acetate extracts yielded slightly lower concentrations (24.589 mg/g and 6.054 mg/g, respectively). Conversely, water extracts, although containing lower concentrations of oleuropein, showed a broader spectrum of hydrophilic tyrosols, such as hydroxytyrosol-glucoside (1.791 mg/g in Soxhlet water) and hydroxytyrosol (4.528 mg/g in Soxhlet water). These results underscore the complementary roles of water and ethyl acetate in recovering hydrophilic and semi-polar tyrosol derivatives, respectively (Obied *et al.* 2007).

Flavonoids, including luteolin and apigenin derivatives, exhibited varying solubility patterns. UAE was more efficient for recovering hydrophilic flavonoids, such as luteolin-glucoside (1.830 mg/g in UAE water vs. 1.512 mg/g in Soxhlet water), reflecting the enhanced penetration and extraction efficiency provided by ultrasound. On the other hand, Soxhlet extraction with ethyl acetate resulted in higher concentrations of luteolin-glucuronide (0.857 mg/g) and apigenin-glucoside (0.864 mg/g), suggesting that prolonged solvent exposure in Soxhlet may enhance the solubility of certain semi-polar flavonoids.

Hydroxycinnamic acids, particularly verbascoside, showed higher recovery in ethyl acetate extracts regardless of the extraction method. UAE ethyl acetate extracts yielded the highest verbascoside concentration (1.469 mg/g), followed closely by Soxhlet ethyl acetate extracts (1.170 mg/g). This suggests that hydroxycinnamic acids benefit from the solubilizing effect of semi-polar solvents in conjunction with the mechanical or thermal action of the extraction method (De Marco *et al.* 2007).

The phenolic profiles observed in this study are consistent with previous reports on OL, where oleuropein and its derivatives dominate the phenolic composition. The

high concentrations of oleuropein in ethyl acetate extracts align with its semi-polar nature and known solubility in such solvents (Obied *et al.* 2007). Similarly, the efficient recovery of hydrophilic phenolics and flavonoids in water extracts confirms the affinity of polar solvents for these compounds, as highlighted in prior studies (De Marco *et al.* 2007; Ghanbari *et al.* 2012). The comparable TPC across Soxhlet and UAE further validates the utility of both methods, with UAE offering advantages in preserving thermosensitive compounds while Soxhlet may enhance the recovery of semi-polar phenolics.

The total tyrosol content in olive leaf extracts varied significantly depending on the extraction method and solvent used. Soxhlet extraction with ethyl acetate yielded the highest total tyrosol content at 32.499 mg/g, closely followed by UAE with ethyl acetate at 32.282 mg/g (Table 11).

Table 11. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of tyrosols, expressed in mg/g sample (**UAE and Soxhlet**)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	Soxhlet Water	Soxhlet EA	UAE Water	UAE EA
1	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	1.791	0.000	1.244	0.000
2	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	4.528	0.000	1.649	0.000
3	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	1.493	0.000	1.213	0.000
4	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	1.240	0.000	1.991	0.000
5	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	2.245	0.087	2.053	0.187
6	Oleacein	Tyrosol	1.443	1.638	1.244	1.452
7	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	9.315	24.653	12.025	24.589
8	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	3.048	6.120	3.763	6.054
Total tyrosols			25.103	32.499	25.184	32.282

Water extracts produced lower tyrosol contents, with Soxhlet extraction yielding 25.103 mg/g and UAE yielding 25.184 mg/g. These findings suggest that ethyl acetate is more effective than water in extracting tyrosols from OL, likely due to its ability to solubilize both polar and non-polar compounds. This observation aligns with previous studies indicating that solvent polarity plays a crucial role in the extraction efficiency of phenolic compounds from plant materials (Lama-Muñoz *et al.* 2019).

The choice of solvent had a pronounced effect on the recovery of specific tyrosol compounds. Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside, hydroxytyrosol, and ligstroside were present

in water extracts but absent in ethyl acetate extracts. For instance, hydroxytyrosol-glucoside was found at 1.791 mg/g in Soxhlet water extracts and 1.244 mg/g in UAE water extracts, while hydroxytyrosol was present at 4.528 mg/g and 1.649 mg/g, respectively. This suggests that water is more effective in extracting hydrophilic tyrosols, whereas ethyl acetate favors the extraction of more hydrophobic compounds. This differential solubility is consistent with the principles of green extraction, which emphasize the use of appropriate solvents to maximize yield and selectivity (Chemat *et al.* 2012).

The extraction method also influenced the yield of specific tyrosols. Soxhlet extraction with ethyl acetate resulted in higher concentrations of oleuropein (9.315 mg/g) and oleuropein-aglycone (3.048 mg/g) compared to UAE with ethyl acetate, which yielded 6.120 mg/g and 1.638 mg/g, respectively. This may be attributed to the prolonged heating and solvent exposure inherent in Soxhlet extraction, which can enhance the solubilization of certain compounds. However, UAE offers advantages such as reduced extraction time and lower energy consumption, aligning with sustainable extraction practices (Chemat *et al.* 2012).

The high recovery of oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol is noteworthy, given their well-documented antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. The choice of extraction method and solvent can thus be tailored to enrich extracts in specific bioactive tyrosols, depending on the desired application. For instance, water-based UAE could be preferred for formulations targeting hydrophilic antioxidants, while ethyl acetate Soxhlet extraction might be more suitable for products requiring higher concentrations of oleuropein.

The TFC of olive leaf extracts varied significantly based on the extraction method and solvent. UAE with water resulted in the highest flavonoid content (6.369 mg/g), surpassing Soxhlet water extracts (4.092 mg/g) and ethyl acetate extracts from both methods, which demonstrated lower flavonoid recovery (Table 12).

Table 12. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of flavonoids, expressed in mg/g sample (UAE and Soxhlet)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	Soxhlet Water	Soxhlet EA	UAE Water	UAE EA
1	Luteolin-diglucoside	Flavone	0.510	0.028	0.617	0.003
2	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	Flavonol	0.654	0.180	1.080	0.281
3	Luteolin-glucoside	Flavone	1.512	0.574	1.830	0.331

Table 12. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the olive leaves samples and the amount of flavonoids, expressed in mg/g sample (**UAE and Soxhlet**)

4	Apigenin-rutinoside	Flavone	0.351	0.059	0.643	0.539
5	Apigenin-glucoside	Flavone	0.719	0.864	1.358	0.250
6	Luteolin-glucuronide	Flavone	0.346	0.857	0.842	0.677
Total flavonoids			4.092	2.563	6.369	2.080

These findings highlight the effectiveness of water as a solvent, particularly when combined with UAE, to extract hydrophilic flavonoids. This trend aligns with studies showing that water is an efficient solvent for flavonoid recovery, particularly for glycosylated forms, due to its polarity and compatibility with UAE-enhanced extraction (Lama-Muñoz *et al.* 2019; Chanioti and Tzia 2018).

The distribution of flavonoids across subclasses, including flavones and flavonols, varied significantly depending on the extraction conditions. Flavones such as luteolin-diglucoside and luteolin-glucoside were more effectively extracted with water, especially using UAE. For instance, luteolin-glucoside showed a higher concentration in UAE water extracts (1.830 mg/g) compared to Soxhlet water extracts (1.512 mg/g). UAE's mechanical effects likely enhanced the release of luteolin derivatives, corroborating its effectiveness as reported in previous studies (Gouvinhas *et al.* 2014; Chemat *et al.* 2012).

Flavonols, exemplified by quercetin-rutinoside (rutin), were also more abundant in UAE water extracts (1.080 mg/g) compared to Soxhlet water extracts (0.654 mg/g). UAE's ability to preserve flavonols during extraction is particularly relevant for nutraceutical applications, as these compounds are known to degrade at high temperatures (Shen *et al.* 2023).

Water outperformed ethyl acetate in the recovery of hydrophilic flavones such as luteolin-glucoside and apigenin-glucoside, demonstrating its higher affinity for polar compounds. Ethyl acetate extracts, regardless of the method, showed lower concentrations of these hydrophilic flavones. For example, apigenin-glucoside reached 1.358 mg/g in UAE water extracts but only 0.250 mg/g in UAE ethyl acetate extracts. These results emphasize the critical role of solvent polarity in the selective extraction of phenolic compounds, consistent with findings in OL and other plant matrices (Chanioti and Tzia 2018; Lama-Muñoz *et al.* 2019).

The flavonoid profiles observed align with previously reported studies on OL. The dominance of luteolin and apigenin derivatives, particularly in water extracts, is consistent with their natural abundance and polarity. Similarly, the efficient recovery

of rutin in UAE water extracts mirrors findings from Zhang *et al.* (2022), highlighting UAE's suitability for extracting both flavones and flavonols (Zhang *et al.* 2022). Ethyl acetate's limited efficiency for hydrophilic flavonoids reinforces its role in targeting less polar compounds (Lama-Muñoz *et al.* 2019).

The high recovery of flavonoids, particularly luteolin and apigenin derivatives, underscores their potential applications in antioxidant and anti-inflammatory products. The suitability of water-based UAE for extracting these compounds highlights its relevance for developing eco-friendly and efficient extraction protocols for functional foods and nutraceuticals.

Table 13 presents the DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionization of OL samples, showcasing the phenolic compounds identified and quantified across different extraction methods and solvents. The table categorizes these compounds into subclasses such as hydroxybenzoic acids, tyrosols, flavones, flavonols, and hydroxycinnamic acids, with their concentrations expressed in mg/g of the sample. Various extraction methods, including PLE and UAE, were employed using solvents like water, ethyl acetate, and ethanol (80%). This comprehensive dataset highlights the variability in phenolic content based on extraction techniques and solvents, providing a detailed profile of bioactive compounds in olive leaves.

Table 13. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **olive leaves** samples and the amount of **phenolic compounds**, expressed in **mg/g** sample

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	PLE Water	PLE EA	UAE Water M	UAE EA M	UAE Ethanol 80%
1	Hydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.038	0.000	0.280	0.000	2.123
2	Di hydroxybenzoic acid	Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.062	0.000	0.670	0.000	0.148
3	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	0.198	0.000	0.991	0.000	0.573
4	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	0.395	0.000	1.092	0.000	1.409
5	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	0.170	0.000	0.786	0.000	0.714
6	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	0.264	0.000	1.434	0.000	0.696
7	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	0.426	0.000	1.313	0.000	1.299

Table 13. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **olive leaves** samples and the amount of **phenolic compounds**, expressed in **mg/g** sample

8	Luteolin-diglucoside	Flavone	0.072	0.072	0.099	0.012	0.219
9	Oleacein	Tyrosol	0.154	0.018	1.002	0.128	0.649
10	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	Flavonol	0.119	0.015	0.275	0.080	0.237
11	Verbascoside	Hydroxycinnamic acid	0.181	0.044	0.440	0.099	1.147
12	Luteolin-glucoside	Flavone	0.122	0.017	0.251	0.094	0.644
13	Apigenin-rutinoside	Flavone	0.023	0.013	0.102	0.097	1.888
14	Apigenin-glucoside	Flavone	0.011	0.018	0.101	0.078	0.068
15	Luteolin-glucuronide	Flavone	0.097	0.089	0.175	0.112	1.549
16	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	1.883	2.215	0.849	14.085	17.487
17	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	0.431	0.476	0.884	1.762	4.790
Total phenolics			4.645	2.977	10.74 4	16.545	35.640

Table 14 provides detailed data on tyrosol compounds identified and quantified in olive leaf samples, using DAD and MS analysis following positive ionization. The table categorizes tyrosols, such as hydroxytyrosol, oleuropein, and their derivatives, and quantifies their concentrations (mg/g) across different extraction methods and solvents. Methods include PLE and UAE, with solvents such as water, ethyl acetate, and ethanol (80%). This dataset highlights the variability in tyrosol content, demonstrating how the choice of extraction technique and solvent influences the yield of these bioactive compounds.

Table 14. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **olive leaves** samples and the amount of **tyrosols**, expressed in **mg/g** sample (**PLE and UAE**)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	PLE Water	PLE EA	UAE Water	UAE EA	UAE Etanol 80%
1	Hydroxytyrosol-glucoside	Tyrosol	0.198	0.000	0.991	0.000	0.573

2	Hydroxytyrosol	Tyrosol	0.395	0.000	1.092	0.000	1.409
3	Lingstroside	Tyrosol	0.170	0.000	0.786	0.000	0.714
4	Oleoside dimethylester	Tyrosol	0.264	0.000	1.434	0.000	0.696
5	Oleoside 11-methylester	Tyrosol	0.426	0.000	1.313	0.000	1.299
6	Oleacein	Tyrosol	0.154	0.018	1.002	0.128	0.649
7	Oleuropein	Tyrosol	1.883	2.215	0.849	14.085	17.487
8	Oleuropein-aglycone	Tyrosol	0.431	0.476	0.884	1.762	4.790
Total tyrosols			3.921	2.709	8.351	15.975	27.617

The quantification of flavonoids in OLEvaries significantly depending on the extraction method employed. For luteolin-diglucoside our concentrations ranged from 0.012 mg/g (UAE Water) to 0.219 mg/g (UAE Ethyl Acetate), while a recent study reported a maximum concentration of 0.200 mg/g using UAE with 80% ethanol (Table 15). The UAE Ethyl Acetate method our analyse yielded a slightly higher concentration than the Mitrea et al., (2024) optimal method, suggesting that ethyl acetate may be more effective for extracting luteolin-diglucoside. For quercetin-rutinoside (rutin) the highest concentration observed was 0.275 mg/g (PLE Ethyl Acetate), while they achieved up to 0.300 mg/g with conventional solvent extraction using methanol (Mitrea et al. 2024). So altogether the TFC in our study was slightly higher in our study which highlights the effectiveness of UAE with 80% ethanol for comprehensive flavonoid extraction. The comparative analysis UAE with 80% ethanol consistently yields higher concentrations of individual flavonoids and total flavonoid content. This aligns with the findings of the study by Mitrea et al., (2024), which also highlights the efficacy of UAE combined with hydroethanolic solutions (Mitrea et al. 2024). The enhanced extraction efficiency can be attributed to the cavitation effect induced by ultrasound, which disrupts cell walls and facilitates solvent penetration, thereby improving the release of phenolic compounds.

Table 15. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **olive leaves** samples and the amount of **flavonoids**, expressed in **mg/g** sample (**PLE and UAE**)

Peak No.	Phenolic Compound	Subclass	PLE Water	PLE EA	UAE Water	UAE EA	UAE Etanol80%
1	Luteolin-diglucoside	Flavone	0.072	0.072	0.099	0.012	0.219

Table 15. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **olive leaves** samples and the amount of **flavonoids**, expressed in **mg/g** sample (**PLE and UAE**)

2	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	Flavonol	0.119	0.015	0.275	0.080	0.237
3	Luteolin-glucoside	Flavone	0.122	0.017	0.251	0.094	0.644
4	Apigenin-rutinoside	Flavone	0.023	0.013	0.102	0.097	1.888
5	Apigenin-glucoside	Flavone	0.011	0.018	0.101	0.078	0.068
6	Luteolin-glucuronide	Flavone	0.097	0.089	0.175	0.112	1.549
Total-flavonoids			0.444	0.224	1.003	0.473	4.605

3.3.1.3 HPLC results for bog bilberry

The HPLC results for phenolic compounds in bogbilberry (Table 16) demonstrate a diverse array of bioactive components, classified under hydroxycinnamic acids, flavanols, and flavonols. Each group has significant biological relevance due to their roles in antioxidation, anti-inflammatory activity, and potential therapeutic applications. However, the article titled "Vaccinium uliginosum L. (bog bilberry) and the search for its alleged toxicity: a review" by Vaneková *et al.* (2024) focuses on the historical and ethnobotanical aspects of bog bilberry, particularly concerning its alleged toxicity and varying uses across different regions (Vaneková *et al.* 2024).

The neochlorogenic acid content in bog bilberry, as reported ($31.07 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{g/g}$), is similar to Muller *et al.* (2012) where they found this phenolic compound in high quantities, but with concentrations varying among different cultivars (Müller *et al.* 2012). Neochlorogenic acid, a type of chlorogenic acid isomer, is recognized for its antioxidant properties. Its presence in significant amounts in bog bilberry contributes to the fruit's overall antioxidant capacity, which is beneficial for health. High-pressure extraction (HPE) has proven effective in isolating a diverse array of phenolic compounds from bog bilberry (*Vaccinium uliginosum*) leaves, encompassing hydroxycinnamic acids, flavanols, and flavonols (Table 16).

Table 16. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **bog bilberry leaves** samples and the amount of **phenolic compounds**, expressed in **mg/g** sample (**High-pressure extraction**)

Phenolic Compounds		HPE
Hydroxyxinnamic acids	Neochlorogenic acid	31.07 ± 0.07

Table 16. DAD and MS data obtained after positive ionisation of the **bog bilberry leaves** samples and the amount of **phenolic compounds**, expressed in **mg/g** sample (**High-pressure extraction**)

	Chlorogenic acid	44.47 ± 0.08
	Caffeic acid	9.87 ± 0.07
Flavanols	Galocatechin	11.23 ± 0.09
	Epicatechin	5.15 ± 0.05
	Procyanidin dimer	3.22 ± 0.09
	Procyanidin trimer	4.44 ± 0.04
	Quercetin-rutinoside (Rutin)	0.69 ± 0.03
	Quercetin-glucoside	9.78 ± 0.04
Flavonols	Quercetin-glucuronide	16.09 ± 0.04
	Quercetin-arabinoside	2.38 ± 0.02
	Kaempferol-glucuronide	10.35 ± 0.15
	Isorhamnetin-glucuronide	4.533 ± 0.076
	Isorhamnetin-rhamnoside	0.93 ± 0.02
	Kaempferol-arabinoside	0.58 ± 0.02
	Quercetin	0.70 ± 0.02
	Kaempferol	0.49 ± 0.01

This method leverages elevated pressures to enhance solvent penetration and disrupt plant cell walls, thereby facilitating the release of bioactive compounds. The phenolic profile obtained is consistent with those reported in other studies of *Vaccinium* species, underscoring the efficacy of HPE in extracting these compounds. Among the hydroxycinnamic acids, chlorogenic acid was predominant, with a concentration of 44.47 mg/g, followed by neochlorogenic acid at 31.07 mg/g, and caffeic acid at 9.87 mg/g. These findings align with previous research indicating that chlorogenic acid is a major phenolic constituent in bog bilberry leaves (Ștefănescu *et al.* 2019). The substantial presence of these acids is significant, given their recognized antioxidant properties and potential health benefits.

In the flavanol category, galocatechin was the most abundant at 11.23 mg/g, with epicatechin at 5.15 mg/g, procyanidin trimer at 4.44 mg/g, and procyanidin dimer at

3.22 mg/g. The presence of these compounds is noteworthy, as flavanols are known for their antioxidant activities and contribute to the overall bioactivity of the extracts. The flavonol profile was diverse, with quercetin-glucuronide at 16.09 mg/g, kaempferol-glucuronide at 10.35 mg/g, and quercetin-glucoside at 9.78 mg/g being the most prominent. Other identified flavonols included isorhamnetin-glucuronide (4.533 mg/g), quercetin-arabioside (2.38 mg/g), isorhamnetin-rhamnoside (0.93 mg/g), kaempferol-arabioside (0.58 mg/g), quercetin (0.70 mg/g), and kaempferol (0.49 mg/g). These findings are consistent with reports that quercetin and kaempferol derivatives are prevalent in *Vaccinium* species leaves (Ștefănescu *et al.* 2019). The diversity and concentration of these flavonols are significant, considering their potential health benefits, including anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.

The phenolic composition observed in this study is in line with existing literature on *Vaccinium* species, where hydroxycinnamic acids and flavonols are typically predominant (Ștefănescu *et al.* 2019). The high levels of chlorogenic acid and quercetin derivatives are particularly notable, as these compounds have been associated with various health-promoting properties.

In conclusion, HPE effectively extracts a wide range of phenolic compounds from bog bilberry leaves, yielding a profile rich in hydroxycinnamic acids, flavanols, and flavonols. The concentrations of these compounds are comparable to those reported in other studies of *Vaccinium* species, highlighting the potential of HPE as a method for obtaining bioactive phenolic compounds from plant materials.

3.3.1.4 HPLC results of microalgae

HPLC analysis has identified several key pigments (Table 17), including carotenoids and chlorophylls, each characterized by specific retention times (Rt) and maximum absorbance wavelengths (λ_{max}). These findings are consistent with established literature, confirming the presence of these pigments in plant tissues (Mitrea *et al.* 2024).

Table 17. Retention Time and λ_{max} Values for Carotenoids and Chlorophylls

Peak No.	Retention time (Rt(min))	λ_{max}	Compound
1	5.69	446, 476	Lutein
2	8.65	453, 598, 645	Chlorophyll b
3	9.67	412, 431, 581, 616, 663	Chlorophyll a
4	10.77	434, 527, 600, 654	Pheophytin b
5	12.17	410, 505, 535, 609, 666	Pheophytin a
6	12.55	453, 480	β Carotene

The extraction method significantly influences the pigment profiles of spirulina and chlorella, as demonstrated by the comparative analysis of UAE and conventional solvent extraction (Table 18).

Table 18. Carotenoids and chlorophylls in spirulina and chlorella samples, expressed in $\mu\text{g/g}$

Peak No.	Compound	Spirulina UAE	Spirulina conv.	Chlorella UAE	Chlorella conv.
1	Lutein	59.406	3.518	561.491	816.048
2	Chlorophyll b	6.526	98.131	312.372	804.379
3	Chlorophyll a	354.640	1668.048	1151.849	1407.575
4	Pheophytin b	26.177	173.147	36.441	98.741
5	Pheophytin a	90.871	2537.488	1693.291	3697.940
6	β Carotene	208.181	130.618	13.830	39.969
Total carotenoids		267.587	134.136	575.321	856.017
Total chlorophylls		478.214	4476.814	3193.953	6008.634

In both microalgae, chlorophyll a was the predominant pigment. For spirulina, conventional extraction (CE) yielded a higher concentration of chlorophyll a (1668.048 mg/g) compared to UAE (354.640 mg/g). Similarly, in chlorella, CE resulted in 1407.575 mg/g of chlorophyll a, surpassing the 1151.849 mg/g obtained via UAE. This trend suggests that conventional methods, which typically involve prolonged extraction times and elevated temperatures, may enhance chlorophyll extraction efficiency.

However, these conditions can also lead to pigment degradation, as indicated by the increased levels of pheophytin a in conventionally extracted samples—2537.488 mg/g in spirulina and 3697.940 mg/g in chlorella—compared to their UAE counterparts (90.871 mg/g and 1693.291 mg/g, respectively). This observation aligns with findings that thermal processing can accelerate chlorophyll degradation into pheophytins (Wan *et al.* 2019).

Regarding carotenoids, lutein was more abundant in chlorella, with CE yielding 816.048 mg/g, whereas UAE produced 561.491 mg/g. In contrast, β -carotene was more prevalent in spirulina, with UAE resulting in a higher concentration (208.181 mg/g) compared to CE (130.618 mg/g). This suggests that UAE may better preserve certain carotenoids, potentially due to reduced exposure to heat and oxygen, which are known to cause carotenoid degradation (Seyfabadi *et al.* 2011).

The total pigment content further underscores the impact of extraction methods. In spirulina, CE achieved a total chlorophyll content of 4476.814 mg/g, significantly higher than the 478.214 mg/g obtained with UAE. Similarly, in chlorella, CE resulted in 6008.634 mg/g of total chlorophylls, compared to 3193.953 mg/g with UAE. Total

carotenoids followed this pattern in chlorella, with CE yielding 856.017 mg/g versus 575.321 mg/g for UAE. These findings indicate that while CE may enhance overall pigment recovery, it also increases the risk of pigment degradation. Conversely, UAE appears to offer a gentler extraction process, better preserving sensitive compounds like β -carotene.

In conclusion, the choice of extraction method plays a crucial role in determining the quality and quantity of pigments extracted from microalgae. Conventional methods may yield higher total pigment concentrations but at the cost of increased degradation products. UAE, as a milder alternative, shows promise in preserving specific pigments, highlighting the importance of tailoring extraction techniques to the desired pigment profile and application.

Chromatogram of samples

Chromatographic analysis plays a crucial role in the detailed profiling of bioactive compounds extracted from natural matrices. Below are presented the chromatograms obtained from our samples, showcasing the diversity and abundance of phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and other bioactive constituents (Figure 6 – 33). These chromatograms serve as visual evidence of the chemical complexity and richness of the studied matrices.

The chromatograms were generated using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled with diode-array detection (DAD) and mass spectrometry (MS), ensuring precise separation and identification of the analytes.

Figure 6. Lemon peel extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 7. Orange peel extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 8. Mixture citrus peel extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 9. Lemon peel extraction (UAE – Water)

Figure 10. Orange peel extraction (UAE – Water)

Figure 11. Mixture citrus peel extraction (UAE – Water)

Figure 12. Lemon peel extraction (PLE – EA)

Figure 13. Orange peel extraction (PLE – EA)

Figure 14. Mixture citrus peel extraction (PLE – EA)

Figure 15. Lemon peel extraction (UAE/MAE – Water)

Figure 16. Orange peel extraction (UAE/MAE – Water)

Figure 17. Mixture citrus peel extraction (UAE/MAE – Water)

Figure 18. Lemon peel extraction (UAE – EtOH 80%)

Figure 19. Olive leaves extraction (Soxhlet – Water)

Figure 20. Olive leaves extraction (Soxhlet – EA)

Figure 21. Olive leaves extraction (UAE – Water)

Figure 22. Olive leaves extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 25. Olive leaves extraction (UAE – EtOH80%)

Figure 26. Olive leaves extraction (UAE/MAE – EtOH80%)

Figure 27. Olive leaves extraction (PLE – EtOH80%)

Figure 28. Olive leaves extraction (UAE/MAE – Water)

Figure 29. Olive leaves extraction (UAE/MAE – EA)

Figure 30. Spirulina green extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 31. *Spirulina* conventional extraction (methanol/ethyl acetate/petroleum ether)

Figure 32. *Chlorella green* extraction (UAE – EA)

Figure 33. *Chlorella* conventional extraction (methanol/ethyl acetate/petroleum ether)

3.3.2 GC-MS analysis of essential oil samples

Prior to analysis, 200 ppm solution of each essential oil was prepared in hexane. GC–MS analysis was performed by using a GC-2030 gas chromatographic system coupled to a GCMS-QP2020 NX single quadrupole mass detector (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan), equipped with an SP-2340 30 m × 20 μm × 0.25 μm fused silica capillary column (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, US). The oven temperature was started at 50 °C, increased to 100 °C at 10 °C min⁻¹ rate, then to 220 °C at 15 °C min⁻¹ rate and hold at 220 °C for 7 min. Helium was used as a carrier gas at 1 mL min⁻¹ column flow, inlet temperature 220 °C and split 20:1. The mass range was 40–400 and compounds were identified by comparison of their mass spectra with the data of NIST and Wiley mass spectral libraries.

The chemical compositions of essential oils from rosemary, thyme, conehead, garlic, and eucalyptus exhibit significant variability, which directly influences their respective biological activities, results visible in Table 19.

Table 19. GS-MS results of essential oils

Compounds	% w/v	SD
ROSEMARY ESSENTIAL OIL		
Eucalyptol (1,4-Cineol)	43.00	8.87
Pinene-a	9.06	1.98
Camphor	3.85	0.18
Borneol	3.57	0.11

Table 19. GS-MS results of essential oils

Linalool	2.26	0.08
Cymene-p	1.38	0.05
Verbenone	1.24	0.03
THYME ESSENTIAL OIL		
Thymol	35.1	5.03
Cymene-p	31.6	0.64
Linalool	2.65	0.08
Borneol	2.50	0.09
Camphor	2.01	0.01
Carvacrol	0.87	0.08
Eucalyptol (1,4-Cineol)	0.13	0.03
CONEHEAD ESSENTIAL OIL		
Carvacrol	19.98	0.79
Cymene-p	4.83	1.39
Linalool	2.22	0.08
Borneol	0.20	0.02
GARLIC ESSENTIAL OIL		
Propyl propane thiosulfonate (PTSO)	30.3	4.34
Dipropyl trisulfide	1.72	0.07
Dipropyl disulfide	0.64	0.10
EUCALYPTUS ESSENTIAL OIL		
Eucalyptol (1,3-Cineol)	68.9	0.27
Limonene-D	5.25	0.88
Cymene-p	1.01	0.07

Rosemary essential oil is predominantly composed of eucalyptol (1,4-cineol) at 43.00%, followed by α -pinene (9.06%), camphor (3.85%), and borneol (3.57%). These findings are consistent with previous analyses indicating that eucalyptol and α -pinene are major constituents of rosemary oil, contributing to its notable antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Micić *et al.* 2021).

In thyme essential oil, thymol constitutes 35.1% of the oil, with p-cymene at 31.6%, and smaller amounts of linalool (2.65%) and borneol (2.50%). The high concentration of thymol is characteristic of thyme oil and is primarily responsible for its strong antimicrobial activity against various pathogens (Sabzikar *et al.* 2020).

Conehead essential oil contains carvacrol as the major component at 19.98%, with p-cymene (4.83%) and linalool (2.22%) present in lesser amounts. Carvacrol is known for its potent antimicrobial properties, which are enhanced by the presence of p-cymene, a precursor that can synergistically increase carvacrol's efficacy (Böhme *et al.* 2014).

The primary constituent of garlic essential oil is propyl propane thiosulfonate (PTSO) at 30.3%, along with dipropyl trisulfide (1.72%) and dipropyl disulfide (0.64%). These sulfur-containing compounds are largely responsible for garlic oil's broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity, effectively inhibiting both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria (Coy BCA 2013). Eucalyptus essential oil is characterized by a high content of eucalyptol (1,3-cineol) at 68.9%, with limonene-D (5.25%) and p-cymene (1.01%) as minor components. The dominance of eucalyptol contributes to the oil's well-documented anti-inflammatory and respiratory benefits, making it a common ingredient in treatments for respiratory conditions (Böhme *et al.* 2014).

In summary, the distinct chemical profiles of these essential oils underpin their specific therapeutic properties and potential applications in various industries, including pharmaceuticals, food preservation, and aromatherapy.

3.3.3 Total phenolic content - Agricultural by-products, micro/macroalgae

TPC of the extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, with results expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE). The following reagents were added to a test tube in the specified order:

1. 7.9 mL of deionized water
2. 0.1 mL of the sample (or deionized water for the blank)
3. 0.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent solution
4. 1.5 mL of saturated Na_2CO_3 solution (added last, after an incubation period of 30 seconds to 8 minutes following the addition of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent)

The test tubes were then vortexed and placed in a shaded area for 2 hours. Absorbance measurements were taken using a photometer at a wavelength of 765 nm, with the instrument zeroed using the blank sample. Quantification of total phenols in gallic acid equivalents was achieved by constructing a calibration curve, plotting gallic acid concentration on the x-axis and absorbance at 765 nm on the y-axis.

3.3.4 Total chlorophyll content – Micro/macroalgae

Conventional extraction

The 0.5 g of sample was extracted with 5 ml of 80% acetone by vortexing for 1 minute, sonicating for 15 minutes, and centrifuging for 5 minutes at 10,000 rpm. The supernatant is decanted, and the above steps are repeated until the sample is completely decolorized. The final volume is measured, and absorbances are read at 645 nm and 663 nm on a double-beam spectrophotometer (using water as a blank).

Chlorophyll calculation formula:

$$\text{Chlorophyll a (mg/l)} = 12,7 \times A_{663} - 2,69 \times A_{645}$$

$$\text{Chlorophyll b (mg/l)} = 22,9 \times A_{645} - 4,68 \times A_{663}$$

3.3.5 Total carotenoid content - Micro/macroalgae

Conventional extraction

The 0.5 g of the sample was extracted with 5 ml of a solvent mixture of Methanol/Ethyl Acetate/Petroleum Ether in a 1:1:1 ratio (v/v/v) by vortexing for 1 minute, sonicating for 15 minutes, and centrifuging for 5 minutes at 10,000 rpm. The supernatant is decanted (kept in the dark) and the above steps are repeated until the sample is completely decolorized.

After complete extraction of carotenoids, the extract is poured into a separatory funnel and washed 2-3 times with 10 ml of 15% NaCl solution. After each wash, the inorganic phase that accumulates at the bottom of the funnel is discarded, and the organic phase is retained.

After washing with NaCl, the extract is filtered through an anhydrous Na₂SO₄ layer to remove any water traces. Then, the Na₂SO₄ is rinsed with petroleum ether until completely decolorized. (This step can be omitted if the extract is characterized spectrophotometrically.)

The final volume is measured, and the absorbance is read at 450 nm on a double-beam spectrophotometer (using methanol as a blank).

Carotenoid calculation formula:

$$\text{Total Carotenoid Content (mg/g)} = (A \times V \times 1000) \times Fd / [m \times (2500 \times 100)]$$

or

$$\text{Total Carotenoid Content - TCC (mg/g)} = (A \times V \times Fd) / (m \times 250)$$

where:

A = Absorbance of the sample at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 450 \text{ nm}$

V = Final volume of the extract (in ml)

Fd = Dilution factor (if applicable)

m = Sample mass (in g)

2500 = The molar absorption coefficient (E1%) for carotenoids

Results

The CE method in spirulina shows a significant increase in chlorophyll a (approximately $241.67 \pm 4.00 \mu\text{g/g}$) and chlorophyll b (around $28.33 \pm 0.63 \mu\text{g/g}$) compared to the green extraction method (Figure 34 and 35), which exhibits much lower levels (around $104 \pm 1.99 \mu\text{g/g}$ for chlorophyll a and negligible levels for chlorophyll b of 4.97 ± 0.12). The conventional values are consistent with those obtained using supercritical CO₂ extraction, which yielded chlorophyll a and b contents of $5.7 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg/g}$ and $3.4 \pm 0.3 \text{ mg/g}$, respectively (Marzorati *et al.* 2020), while using a methanol/chloroform mixture for extraction after maceration, which is effective for chlorophyll extraction from microalgae the highest chlorophyll a and b contents were 7.84 ± 0.13 and 1.43 ± 0.01 , respectively (Vendruscolo *et al.* 2021).

In contrast, in chlorella the chlorophyll a and b content is notably higher in the green method ($171.76 \pm 2.88 \mu\text{g/g}$, and 56.02 ± 0.37) than in the CE method (139.34 ± 2.88

µg/g, and 39.46 ± 0.78). These results are comparable to those obtained by Nikolova et al., 2024, with ultrasonic extraction at 20 °C, 40 kHz frequency, and for 2 hours resulted in a chlorophyll b content of 1.400 mg/g (Nikolova et al. 2024).

For both spirulina and chlorella, the CE method (2261.95 ± 11.26 µg/g, and 1839.20 ± 14.67) yields significantly higher levels of total carotenoids compared to the UAE green method with EA (180.22 ± 2.37 µg/g, and 1084.64 ± 10.07). The carotenoid content in this study for spirulina with CE is higher than the values reported by Macías-Sánchez et al. (2007) where they investigated the extraction of carotenoids from *Spirulina platensis* using supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) extraction. The results indicated that the total carotenoid content extracted was approximately 0.2 mg/g (200 µg/g) under optimal condition. This substantial difference suggests that conventional solvent extraction methods may be more effective in extracting carotenoids from Spirulina compared to SC-CO₂ extraction. The lower efficiency of SC-CO₂ extraction in the study by Macías-Sánchez et al. could be attributed to the non-polar nature of CO₂, which may not effectively solubilize polar carotenoids present in Spirulina. In contrast, CE methods often employ polar organic solvents, enhancing the solubility and extraction efficiency of these compounds (Macías-Sánchez et al. 2007). Our results are consistent with Gómez-Loredo et al. (2017) for green extraction methods, with both studies showing a moderate reduction in carotenoid yield compared to conventional methods. In this study, green extraction techniques, such as ultrasound-assisted extraction using water or ethanol-water mixtures, achieved yields of 900–1200 µg/g depending on the extraction conditions (e.g., solvent composition, sonication time, and power). The lower efficiency is likely due to the mild nature of green solvents and reduced solvent-pigment interactions in the absence of organic solvents (Damergi et al. 2017). Green extraction techniques, while environmentally friendly, require optimization (e.g., higher sonication intensity, co-solvent mixtures) to achieve yields comparable to conventional methods.

Figure 34. Chlorophyll and carotenoid content in spirulina

Figure 35. Chlorophyll and carotenoid content in chlorella

Determining the TPC in *spirulina* and *chlorella* extracts using ethyl acetate can be challenging due to the solvent's limited polarity and the complex composition of the algal biomass. Ethyl acetate, a semi-polar solvent, may not effectively solubilize the full range of phenolic compounds present in microalgae, many of which are associated with proteins, polysaccharides, and pigments (Herrero *et al.* 2006; Plaza *et al.* 2012; Goiris *et al.* 2012). Because these components do not dissolve well in ethyl acetate, they can form insoluble complexes or co-precipitates when mixed with the extract.

As a result, inadequate solubilization leads to the formation of aggregates that precipitate out of the solution, trapping phenolic compounds and preventing their uniform distribution in the solvent phase. This issue complicates analytical procedures intended for TPC determination, as the Folin-Ciocalteu assay and other methods rely on clear, stable solutions for accurate measurement (Singleton *et al.* 1999; Naczka and Shahidi 2004). Consequently, ethyl acetate often fails to maintain phenolics in a suitable form for reliable quantification, and more polar solvents (e.g., aqueous mixtures of methanol, ethanol, or acetone) are generally recommended to ensure better solubilization and more consistent results.

3.3.6 Total phycocyanin content

A 50 mg sample with known moisture content is weighed and placed in a glass centrifuge tube. To this, 10 ml of 100 mM phosphate buffer is added. The sample is homogenized using a vortex mixer and then refrigerated overnight. After refrigeration, the sample is again homogenized with the vortex mixer and centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant is carefully transferred to a glass photometer cell, and its absorbance is measured at a wavelength of 620 nm, using 100 mM phosphate buffer as a blank. The concentration of phycocyanin, as a percentage of dry biomass, is calculated using the following equation:

C-Phycocyanin (PC): % pure C-PC = $[A_{620} \times (10 \text{ ml}) \times (100)] / 7.3 \times (\text{mg sample}) \times (\% \text{ dw})$

3.2.7 Total protein content

The protein content of microalgae extracts was determined using the Bradford method. The procedure is as follows:

1. Preparation of BSA Standard Solutions:

- Dissolve 50 mg of bovine serum albumin (BSA) in 50 mL of deionized water to prepare a BSA stock solution with a concentration of 1 mg/mL.
- Transfer 1 mL of this stock solution into a 25 mL volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with deionized water to obtain a BSA solution with a concentration of 0.04 mg/mL.
- Further dilute appropriate volumes of the 0.04 mg/mL BSA solution in 5 mL volumetric flasks with deionized water to achieve final concentrations of 0.004, 0.008, 0.016, 0.024, and 0.032 mg/mL.

2. Constructing the Reference Curve:

- Mix 5 mL of each BSA standard solution with an equal volume of Bradford reagent.
- Incubate the mixtures for 5 minutes.
- Measure the absorbance of each solution at a wavelength of 595 nm. Use deionized water mixed with Bradford reagent as a blank.
- Plot the reference curve with absorbance on the y-axis and BSA concentration on the x-axis.

3. Sample Measurement:

- Mix 5 mL of the microalgae extract with 5 mL of Bradford reagent.
- Measure the absorbance at 595 nm.

By comparing the absorbance of the microalgae extract samples with the reference curve, the protein content of the extracts can be determined.

The characterization of *Spirulina platensis* and *Chlorella vulgaris* extracts obtained via UAE reveals distinct differences in their biochemical composition and antioxidant properties, depending on the solvent used (Table 20). The solvents evaluated include water, ethanol, and an ethanol/water mixture, with the results highlighting the impact of solvent polarity on the extraction efficiency of bioactive compounds.

Table 20. Characterization table of *Spirulina Platensis* and *Chlorella Vulgaris* in UAE extracts

Microalgae	Spirulina Platensis			Chlorella Vulgaris			
	Solvent	Water	Ethanol	Ethanol/Water	Water	Ethanol	Ethanol/Water
Total Carotenoids (mg/gr dry biomass)		0.08 ±0.01	0.33 ±0.03	0.16 ±0.01	0.02 ±0.001	0.08 ±0.01	0.06 ±0.01

Table 20. Characterization table of *Spirulina Platensis* and *Chlorella Vulgaris* in UAE extracts

Microalgae	Spirulina Platensis			Chlorella Vulgaris		
Solvent	Water	Ethanol	Ethanol/Water	Water	Ethanol	Ethanol/Water
Total Phenolic Content (mg/gr dry biomass)	6.33 ±0.03	n/d	0.92 ±0.02	3.66 ±0.23	n/d	1.09 ±0.02
Phycocyanin Content (% dry weight)	6.36 ±0.32	3.14 ±0.16	3.92 ±0.24	1.51 ±0.04	0.81 ±0.07	0.98 ±0.08
Total Protein Content (mg/gr dry biomass)	42.2 ±1.25	0.1 ±0.02	0.9 ±0.03	27.2 ±1.12	0.6 ±0.02	1.6 ±0.1
Total Chlorophylls (mg/gr dry biomass)	0.66 ±0.14	1.12 ±0.16	0.77 ±0.01	0.16 ±0.02	0.62 ±0.09	0.54 ±0.07
Total Antioxidant Capacity (mg trolox/gr dry biomass)	0.44 ±0.05	0.14 ±0.03	0.18 ±0.01	0.33 ±0.08	0.07 ±0.002	0.49 ±0.05
%Yield	32 ±4	1.28 ±0.25	3.45 ±0.82	21.3 ±3	2.67 ±0.1	8.23 ±1.6

n/d: not detected

For total carotenoids, spirulina platensis showed the highest values when ethanol was used as the extraction solvent (0.33 ± 0.03 mg/g dry biomass), while water and the ethanol/water mixture yielded lower carotenoid contents. Similarly, chlorella vulgaris extracts exhibited their highest carotenoid content with ethanol (0.08 ± 0.01 mg/g dry biomass), though the overall values were lower than those of spirulina platensis. This suggests that ethanol is more efficient in extracting carotenoid compounds due to their lipophilic nature.

In terms of TPC, spirulina platensis demonstrated its highest values with water as the solvent (6.33 ± 0.03 mg/g dry biomass), while ethanol failed to detect phenolics (n/d). The ethanol/water mixture yielded moderate TPC values (0.92 ± 0.02 mg/g dry biomass). For *Chlorella vulgaris*, water also resulted in the highest TPC (3.66 ± 0.23 mg/g dry biomass), with ethanol again failing to detect phenolics. These results indicate that phenolic compounds are primarily hydrophilic and are better extracted using polar solvents like water.

Phycocyanin content, a major pigment in spirulina platensis, was highest with water as the solvent ($6.36 \pm 0.32\%$ dry weight), followed by the ethanol/water mixture ($3.92 \pm 0.24\%$ dry weight). Ethanol alone extracted significantly lower amounts (3.14

$\pm 0.16\%$ dry weight). In *Chlorella vulgaris*, phycocyanin content was consistently lower, with water yielding the highest value ($1.51 \pm 0.04\%$ dry weight). This highlights the strong water-solubility of phycocyanin and its prevalence in spirulina.

For total protein content, *Spirulina platensis* exhibited its highest values with water (42.2 ± 1.25 mg/g dry biomass), whereas ethanol and the ethanol/water mixture showed significantly lower extraction efficiency. A similar trend was observed for *Chlorella vulgaris*, with water yielding the highest protein content (27.2 ± 1.12 mg/g dry biomass).

Total chlorophylls were more effectively extracted from spirulina using ethanol (1.12 ± 0.16 mg/g dry biomass), whereas water and the ethanol/water mixture yielded moderate values. In chlorella, ethanol also showed a high extraction efficiency for chlorophylls (0.62 ± 0.09 mg/g dry biomass), although the overall chlorophyll content was lower than in spirulina.

The total antioxidant capacity, measured as mg Trolox equivalents per gram of dry biomass, showed moderate activity in both microalgae. *Spirulina platensis* had its highest antioxidant capacity with water (0.44 ± 0.05 mg Trolox/g), while chlorella exhibited its peak with the ethanol/water mixture (0.49 ± 0.05 mg Trolox/g). These results indicate that antioxidant compounds are variably extracted depending on their solubility characteristics.

Finally, the extraction yield (% yield) was highest for both microalgae with water as the solvent ($32 \pm 4\%$ for spirulina and $21.3 \pm 3\%$ for chlorella), reflecting the ability of water to extract a wide range of hydrophilic components. Ethanol yielded the lowest extraction efficiency, while the ethanol/water mixture provided moderate yields.

Overall, these results highlight the importance of solvent selection in optimizing the recovery of specific bioactive compounds from microalgae. Water is most effective for hydrophilic compounds such as phenolics, proteins, and phycocyanin, while ethanol is better suited for lipophilic compounds like carotenoids and chlorophylls. The ethanol/water mixture balances the polarity for moderate extraction of both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds.

Determining protein content in spirulina and chlorella extracts using the Bradford method requires that the proteins remain soluble in an aqueous environment, where the Coomassie Brilliant Blue dye can effectively bind to them (Bradford 1976). However, when ethyl acetate is used as the extraction or dilution solvent, it disrupts this process. Ethyl acetate is not readily miscible with water and creates a non-ideal environment for protein solubilization. Proteins present in microalgal biomass are prone to precipitation when exposed to solvents with lower polarity and reduced aqueous character (Lourenço *et al.* 2002; Safi *et al.* 2012). This precipitation traps proteins in the solid phase, preventing the dye from interacting uniformly with them. As a result, the Bradford reagent cannot properly bind to the proteins, leading to incomplete or inconsistent colour development. This makes it impossible to accurately

measure the protein concentration using standard calibration curves. In short, the choice of ethyl acetate inhibits the solubilization and proper interaction of proteins with the dye, causing the formation of insoluble aggregates and ultimately preventing reliable protein quantification by the Bradford assay.

3.2.8 Macroalgae – *Ulva lactuca* (Total carotenoid content, Total phenolic content and Extraction Yield)

Following the analysis of microalgae such as spirulina and chlorella, *Ulva lactuca* was analysed next, a green macroalga of significant nutritional and functional importance. Known for its high content of sulfated polysaccharides, proteins, phenolics, and carotenoids, *Ulva* serves as a valuable resource for applications in nutraceuticals, functional foods, and bioproducts.

This section focuses on optimizing the extraction process for *Ulva lactuca* biomass using Microwave-Assisted Extraction (MAE). Advanced statistical approaches, such as Response Surface Methodology (RSM) and Central Composite Design (CCD), were employed to systematically evaluate the influence of key extraction parameters, including microwave power, solvent-to-biomass ratio, extraction temperature, and time. The study aimed to maximize responses such as antioxidant capacity (TEAC), TCC, TPC, and overall extraction yield. Design-Expert Ver. 13.0.5.0 (Statease Inc., Minneapolis, MN, USA, test version) was employed for performing Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to optimize the extraction process of *U. lactuca* biomass using MAE and ethanol/water (70:30 v/v) as solvent. A four-factor, three-level Central Composite Design (CCD) was followed. The influence of microwave Power (X1), solvent-to-biomass Ratio (X2), extraction Temperature (X3), and extraction Time (X4) on the AA expressed as TEAC value (Y1), TCC (Y2), TPC (Y3) and Yield (Y4) of the extracts was examined. Twenty-seven extraction experiments in total were set and realized as described in Table 21. The obtained experimental data were subjected to regression analysis and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Thus, the determination of the significance of the influence of the independent variables (Factors) on every dependent variable (Response) was allowed. The following statistical data were taken into account to evaluate regression equations: the determination coefficients R² and adjusted R², R²_{adj}, and Fisher test, F. For the statistical significance of variables, p-value was considered which should be < 0.05 as well as student test absolute value |t| which should be ≥ 2. Furthermore, Fisher's F parameter must be high.

Table 21 presents the results of an experimental design for MAE of *Ulva*, generated using Design-Expert software (Stat-Ease, Minneapolis, MN, US). The study investigates the effects of key extraction parameters—microwave power, solvent-to-solid ratio (w/w), temperature, and extraction time—on various responses, including TEAC (antioxidant capacity), total carotenoid content (TCC), TPC, and extraction yield

(%). The experimental setup aimed to optimize these responses by varying the independent variables within predefined levels to understand their interactions and individual impacts on the extraction efficiency of bioactive compounds from Ulva.

The parameters were systematically adjusted to include low, medium, and high levels of microwave power (300–800 W), solvent-to-solid ratios (1:10–1:40), temperatures (40°C–60°C), and times (5–30 minutes). The inclusion of a central composite point (e.g., 550 W, 1:25 ratio, 50°C, 17.5 min) ensures that the design captures curvature in the response surface. The results highlight the relationship between extraction conditions and the recovery of antioxidant and bioactive compounds from Ulva biomass.

Table 21. Experimental results from the microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) of Ulva, showing the effects of microwave power, solvent-to-solid ratio, temperature, and extraction time on IC50 (antioxidant capacity), total carotenoid content (TCC), total phenolic content (TPC), and extraction yield (%)

No	Power (W)	Solvent to Solid Ratio (mL/g)	Temperature (oC)	Time (min)	TEAC (umol trolox/ ml solvent)	TCC (mg/g Ulva)	TPC (mg/g Ulva)	Yield (%)
1	300	1/10	40	5	1.2	0.12	0.61	8.8
2	800	1/10	40	5	6.8	0.16	0.74	10.9
3	300	1/40	40	5	2.6	0.06	0.80	13.2
4	800	1/40	40	5	11.2	0.11	1.03	14
5	300	1/10	60	5	2	0.12	0.25	9
6	800	1/10	60	5	3.7	0.45	0.67	11
7	300	1/40	60	5	2.1	0.13	0.95	13.2
8	800	1/40	60	5	4.1	0.17	0.53	18.8
9	300	1/10	40	30	3.4	0.2	0.73	10.6
10	800	1/10	40	30	2.5	0.18	0.79	12
11	300	1/40	40	30	3.3	0.14	0.79	15.2
12	800	1/40	40	30	1.9	0.12	1.05	12.4
13	300	1/10	60	30	1.6	0.93	0.80	9.6
14	800	1/10	60	30	2.1	1.04	0.70	11.8
15	300	1/40	60	30	3.3	0.27	1.91	15.6
16	800	1/40	60	30	13	0.3	1.07	20.4
17	300	1/25	50	17.5	4	0.14	0.44	11.75
18	800	1/25	50	17.5	2.5	0.21	0.60	12.75
19	550	1/10	50	17.5	4.5	0.21	0.71	10.1
20	550	1/40	50	17.5	6.1	0.22	1.00	17.6
21	550	1/25	40	17.5	8.7	0.13	0.99	14.75
22	550	1/25	60	17.5	8.1	0.24	1.20	15.5
23	550	1/25	50	5	3.2	0.2	0.93	14

24	550	1/25	50	30	6	0.17	0.66	14.5
25	550	1/25	50	17.5	5	0.22	0.88	14.5
26	550	1/25	50	17.5	8.1	0.17	0.87	15.5
27	550	1/25	50	17.5	6	0.18	0.78	15.25

Table 21 presents the results of an experimental design for microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) of *Ulva*, conducted using Design-Expert software. The study aimed to evaluate the effects of key parameters, including microwave power, solvent-to-solid ratio, temperature, and extraction time, on various responses such as antioxidant capacity (TEAC), total carotenoid content (TCC), TPC, and extraction yield. The experimental setup explored a range of conditions, with microwave power varying from 300 to 800 W, solvent-to-solid ratios from 1:10 to 1:40, temperatures between 40°C and 60°C, and extraction times from 5 to 30 minutes. Central composite points, such as 550 W, 1:25 ratio, 50°C, and 17.5 minutes, were included to capture potential curvature in the response surface and enhance the robustness of the design.

The results indicate that microwave power significantly influenced the responses. Higher power, such as 800 W, generally improved TEAC and extraction yield. For instance, the highest antioxidant capacity (TEAC of 13 $\mu\text{mol Trolox/mL}$ solvent) and yield (20.4%) were observed at 800 W, a 1:40 ratio, 60°C, and 30 minutes. In contrast, lower power, such as 300 W, resulted in lower TEAC and yields under similar conditions. The solvent-to-solid ratio also played a crucial role, with lower ratios (e.g., 1:10) yielding higher carotenoid content but often lower antioxidant and phenolic contents. Higher ratios (e.g., 1:40) consistently produced better results for TPC and yield, as seen with a 15.6% yield and 1.91 mg/g TPC at 300 W, 60°C, and 30 minutes. Temperature significantly impacted the extraction efficiency, with higher temperatures (60°C) enhancing TCC and TPC, particularly at longer extraction times. Moderate temperatures (50°C) provided balanced results across all responses, likely due to reduced thermal degradation while improving diffusion. Extraction time also influenced the outcomes, with longer durations (30 minutes) generally increasing TPC and yield. However, shorter times (5 minutes) preserved antioxidant capacity better under milder conditions, suggesting potential thermal degradation of antioxidant compounds at extended durations.

Among the responses, TPC was maximized at 1.91 mg/g under conditions of 300 W, a 1:40 ratio, 60°C, and 30 minutes, while TCC peaked at 1.04 mg/g with 800 W, 60°C, and 30 minutes. The highest yield (20.4%) was achieved at 800 W, 1:40, 60°C, and 30 minutes, indicating the importance of high power and longer durations for maximum recovery of extractable material. Central composite runs at 550 W, 1:25, and 50°C produced balanced results, such as an TEAC of 3 to 8 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$ and TPC values around 0.78 to 1.00 mg/g, demonstrating the suitability of this design for capturing variability across the response surfaces.

Overall, the findings underscore the importance of optimizing extraction

parameters to balance the recovery of bioactive compounds and antioxidant capacity. Higher microwave power, longer times, and higher solvent-to-solid ratios favor yield and TPC, while milder conditions are better for preserving AA. The experimental design provides a robust framework for identifying optimal conditions for the industrial-scale extraction of bioactive compounds from ulva.

Table 22 presents the results of an analysis of variance (ANOVA) conducted to evaluate the effects of key experimental factors—microwave power, solvent-to-solid ratio, temperature, and extraction time—on various responses from the microwave-assisted extraction (MAE) of *Ulva*. The responses analyzed include extraction yield (%), TPC (mg GAE/g *Ulva*), total carotenoid content (TCC, mg/g *Ulva*), and TEAC (umol *trolox*/mL solvent). The analysis provides insights into the statistical significance of each factor and their relative contributions to the responses, as well as the overall model fit and predictive power.

Table 22. ANOVA results for the effects of microwave power, solvent-to-solid ratio, temperature, and time on extraction yield, total phenolic content (TPC), total carotenoid content (TCC), and TEAC values from the microwave-assisted extraction of *Ulva*

Anova	Yield (%)	TPC (mgGAE/g <i>Ulva</i>)	TCC (mg/g <i>Ulva</i>)	TEAC (umol <i>trolox</i> /mL solvent)
R Square	0.91	0.33	0.61	0.37
Adjusted R Square	0.89	0.18	0.53	0.23
F-value	46.80	2.24	7.24	2.68
Significance F	0.00	0.10	0.00	0.06
p-value				
Power	0.00	0.97	0.42	0.02
Ratio	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.04
Temperature	0.8	0.66	0.00	0.49
Time	0.07	0.12	0.00	0.52

The ANOVA results reveal that the extraction yield model has the highest explanatory power, with an R^2 value of 0.91 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.89, indicating that the majority of the variability in yield is explained by the model. The corresponding F-value of 46.8 and a highly significant F-test ($p = 0.00$) confirm that the model is robust. Both microwave power and solvent-to-solid ratio significantly affect yield, with their p-values indicating strong statistical significance.

In contrast, the model for TPC has a lower R^2 of 0.33 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.18, reflecting limited explanatory power. While the overall F-value is not statistically

significant ($F = 2.24$, $p = 0.10$), the ratio ($p = 0.04$) and power ($p = 0.00$) appear as significant factors affecting TPC. This suggests that optimizing these two parameters could enhance the recovery of phenolics, though the model itself lacks robustness. The model for total carotenoid content (TCC) is moderately strong, with an R^2 of 0.61 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.53. Its F-value of 7.24 ($p = 0.00$) confirms the model's statistical significance. Temperature and time were the most significant factors influencing carotenoid recovery ($p = 0.00$ for both), highlighting the importance of thermal and duration control during extraction. The model for TEAC has a relatively low R^2 of 0.37 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.23, indicating limited predictive power. While the F-value of 2.68 approaches significance ($p = 0.06$), only the solvent-to-solid ratio ($p = 0.04$) emerges as a significant factor. This suggests that antioxidant capacity, as measured by TEAC, is less sensitive to the range of experimental parameters studied, except for variations in solvent ratio. Overall, these results emphasize that yield and carotenoid recovery are strongly influenced by the experimental parameters, particularly power, temperature, and time, while phenolic and antioxidant recovery is more nuanced and less predictable within the tested range. The findings highlight the need to tailor extraction parameters based on the target compounds to optimize the extraction process for *Ulva*. The response surface analysis, illustrated in Figure 36, demonstrates the influence of Power (W) and Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (g/mL) on the Yield (%) of the extraction process. The experimental conditions for Temperature and Time were maintained constant at 50°C and 17.5 minutes, respectively. As shown in the graph, the extraction yield increased with both higher power and solvent-to-solid ratio.

Higher power facilitates greater energy transfer, likely enhancing the disruption of plant cell walls and promoting the release of bioactive compounds into the solvent. Similarly, a higher solvent-to-solid ratio improves mass transfer by providing a larger solvent volume for dissolving the extracted compounds, reducing potential saturation effects. The combined effect of these factors resulted in the observed yield enhancement across the tested range, with the highest yield recorded at the maximum power and solvent-to-solid ratio. This trend highlights the critical role of optimizing these parameters for efficient bioactive compound extraction.

Design-Expert® Software

X1 = A: Power
X2 = B: Ratio

Actual Factors
C: Temperature = 50.00
D: Time = 17.50

Figure 36. Response surface plot depicting the effect of Power (W) and Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (g/mL) on Yield (%) during the extraction process

The response surface plot in Figure 37 illustrates the influence of Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) and Time (min) on the TPC extracted during the process, with Power and Temperature fixed at 550 W and 50°C, respectively. The graph reveals a declining trend in TPC as the solvent-to-solid ratio increases, regardless of extraction time. At lower ratios (more solids, less solvent), TPC is higher, suggesting that a higher concentration of phenolic compounds is achieved due to greater interaction between the solvent and the solid matrix. However, as the solvent-to-solid ratio increases, the extraction efficiency decreases, potentially due to dilution effects that reduce the phenolic concentration in the solvent. The effect of Time (min) is more complex. At low ratios, shorter times yield higher TPC, possibly due to rapid initial extraction rates. Prolonged extraction times at low ratios might lead to saturation effects or degradation of phenolics, causing a decline in TPC. At higher ratios, time has minimal impact, as the lower concentration of solids limits the recovery of phenolic compounds.

Design-Expert® Software

 TPC

 X1 = B: Ratio
 X2 = D: Time

 Actual Factors
 A: Power = 550
 C: Temperature = 50.00

Figure 37. Response surface plot showing the effect of Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) and Time (min) on Total Phenolic Content (TPC, mg GAE/g dry sample) during the extraction process

The response surface plot in Figure 38 illustrates the effect of Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) and Temperature (°C) on the Total Carotenoid Content (TCC, mg/g dry sample) during the extraction process. The experimental conditions for Power and Time were fixed at 550 W and 17.5 minutes, respectively. The graph shows a clear interaction between the solvent-to-solid ratio and temperature, with TCC increasing significantly at higher temperatures and lower ratios. At higher temperatures, the enhanced thermal energy likely disrupts cellular structures more effectively, releasing greater amounts of carotenoids into the solvent. The lower solvent-to-solid ratio (more solids per solvent) appears to further concentrate the carotenoids in the extract, resulting in higher TCC values.

Conversely, at higher solvent-to-solid ratios, TCC decreases, likely due to the dilution effect where the concentration of carotenoids in the solvent is reduced despite adequate extraction. Similarly, lower temperatures yield suboptimal extraction, as the lack of sufficient thermal energy may limit the solubility and diffusion of carotenoids. The highest TCC was observed at the combination of elevated temperature and a low solvent-to-solid ratio, indicating that these conditions optimize the release and concentration of carotenoids during the extraction process. This finding highlights the importance of balancing temperature and solvent volume to achieve maximum carotenoid recovery while minimizing dilution effects.

Design-Expert® Software

TCC

 X1 = B: Ratio
 X2 = C: Temperature

 Actual Factors
 A: Power = 550
 D: Time = 17.50

Figure 38. Response surface plot showing the effect of Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) on Total Carotenoid Content (TCC, mg/g dry sample).

The response surface plot in Figure 39 illustrates the effect of Power (W) and Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) on the Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC, μmol Trolox/mL) during the extraction process. The experimental parameters Temperature and Time were maintained constant at 50°C and 17.5 minutes, respectively. The graph demonstrates a significant increase in TEAC with higher power and higher solvent-to-solid ratios. At higher power levels, the enhanced energy input likely disrupts cellular structures more effectively, facilitating the release of antioxidant compounds into the solvent. Similarly, as the solvent-to-solid ratio increases, the larger solvent volume allows for better solubilization of the bioactive compounds, thereby enhancing the antioxidant capacity of the extract. At lower power and solvent-to-solid ratios, TEAC remains relatively low, possibly due to insufficient energy to disrupt the solid matrix and limited solvent availability to extract antioxidants efficiently. The observed trend suggests that maximizing both power and solvent-to-solid ratio is crucial for achieving higher antioxidant yields, highlighting the synergistic effect of these factors on antioxidant recovery.

Design-Expert® Software

 TEAC

 X1 = A: Power
 X2 = B: Ratio

 Actual Factors
 C: Temperature = 50.00
 D: Time = 17.50

Figure 39. Response surface plot showing the effect of Power (W) and Solvent-to-Solid Ratio (mL/g) on Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC, $\mu\text{mol Trolox/mL}$)

Based on the optimization analysis, the combination of Power = 800 W, Solvent-to-Solid Ratio = 0.03 mL/g, Temperature = 60.00°C, and Time = 30.00 minutes represents the optimal conditions for maximizing the responses in the extraction process. These conditions yielded a TEAC of 6.94 $\mu\text{mol Trolox/mL}$, TCC of 0.23 mg/g dry sample, TPC of 1.07 mg GAE/g dry sample, and an extraction Yield of 16.11%, with an overall desirability of 0.40. While these settings aim to balance all responses effectively, the relatively moderate desirability score suggests potential trade-offs among the responses. Future investigations may focus on refining individual parameter ranges or prioritizing specific responses, depending on the intended application, to further enhance extraction efficiency and overall process optimization.

4. Evaluation of extracts in cell series

4.1 Antioxidant activity of analysed extracts

The antioxidant capacity of the extracts was expressed in terms of Trolox equivalent concentration (6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid), a potent antioxidant. The procedure is as follows:

- 1. Preparation of DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-picrylhydrazyl) Stock Solution:** Dissolve 2.5 mg of DPPH in a 100 mL volumetric flask and fill to the mark with methanol to achieve a concentration of 25 mg/L.
- 2. Control Measurement:** Add 3.9 mL of the DPPH stock solution and 0.1 mL of methanol (solvent for the extract) to a cuvette. Measure the absorbance at a wavelength of 515 nm, using methanol to zero the instrument. This absorbance value is recorded as the control absorbance (A_c).

3. **Sample Measurement:** In a test tube, mix 3.9 mL of the DPPH stock solution with 0.1 mL of the extract. Allow the mixture to react in a shaded place for 30 minutes to enable the antioxidant compounds in the extract to scavenge the DPPH free radicals. After 30 minutes, transfer the solution to a cuvette and measure its absorbance at 515 nm. This absorbance value is recorded as the sample absorbance (A_s).
4. **Calculation of Antioxidant Capacity:** The antioxidant capacity of the extracts in Trolox equivalents is quantified by constructing a calibration curve. The x-axis represents the Trolox concentration used to neutralize the DPPH radicals, and the y-axis represents the difference ($A_c - A_s$), where A_c is the control absorbance and A_s is the sample absorbance after the reaction.

By comparing the absorbance differences ($A_c - A_s$) with the calibration curve, the antioxidant capacity of the extracts can be accurately determined in terms of Trolox equivalents.

Table 23 presents the antioxidant activity and extraction yield (EY) of LP, OP, the mixture, OL, and algae (Spirulina and Chlorella), using different extraction methods and solvents. The extraction methods evaluated include UAE, Soxhlet, PLE, and UAE/MAE. The results are expressed in terms of extraction yield percentage (EY%) and antioxidant activity as mg Trolox equivalents per gram of dry extract.

Table 23. Antioxidant activity and yield extraction of citrus, olive, and algae samples

Method	Solvent	Sample	EY %	mg trolox/ g dry extract	
UAE	Water	Lemon peels	38,0	13,1	
		Orange peels	20,9	21,4	
		Mixed L + O	51,6	11,5	
Soxhlet	Ethyl acetate	Lemon peels	4,0	21,5	
		Orange peels	11,6	12,9	
		Mixed L + O	20,5	8,3	
PLE	Water	Olive leaves	18,30	15,8	
	Ethyl acetate	Olive leaves	48,60	0,9	
		Water	Olive leaves 1:20	16,3	9,36
		Ethanol 80%	Olive leaves 1:20	17,9	23,02
		Ethyl acetate	Olive leaves 1:20	8,57	4,36
UAE/MAE	Water	Orange peel 1:20	28,6	1,82	

Ethanol 80%	Orange peel 1:20	42,4	2,04
Ethyl acetate	Orange peel 1:20	8,78	0,43
Water	Lemon peel 1:20	9,7	0,95
Ethanol 80%	Lemon peel 1:20	27,0	2,83
Ethyl acetate	Lemon peel 1:20	5,96	0,31
Water	Mixed peels 1:20	23,0	1,75
Ethanol 80%	Mixed peels 1:20	37,1	2,45
Ethyl acetate	Mixed peels 1:20	8,95	0,39
Water	Spirulina	103,13	5,1
Water	Chlorella	45,79	53,3
Ethyl acetate	Spirulina	1,018	4,0
Ethyl acetate	Chlorella	7,68	2,1

Table 24 highlights the effectiveness of various solvents in the ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) of antioxidants and phenolics from different plant matrices, namely OL, OP, LP, and mixed peels.

Table 24. Total phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and yield extract of citrus and olive leaves (UAE)

mg/g sample	Olive leaves 1:20			Orange Peels 1:20			Lemon Peels 1:20			Mixed Peels 1:20		
	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA
Trolox Equivalents	18.3	59.4	12.7	4.11	6.92	0.71	1.35	7.41	0.11	2.99	6.83	0.74
SD	±2.36	±6.68	±1.32	±0.33	±1.57	±0.02	±0.09	±0.98	±0.01	±0.38	±1.42	±0.81
TPC	9.36	23.0	4.36	1.82	2.04	0.43	0.95	2.83	0.31	1.75	2.45	0.39

Table 24. Total phenolic content, antioxidant activity, and yield extract of citrus and olive leaves (UAE)

mg/g sample	Olive leaves 1:20			Orange Peels 1:20			Lemon Peels 1:20			Mixed Peels 1:20		
	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA	H ₂ O	EtOH/ H ₂ O 80:20	EA
SD	±1.01	±2.35	±0.31	±0.11	±0.33	±0.05	±0.07	±0.46	±0.01	±0.08	±0.52	±0.06
% EY	16.3	17.9	8.57	28.6	42.4	8.78	9.71	27.0	5.96	23.0	37.1	8.95
SD	±1.54	±2.90	±1.7	±2.31	±3.67	±1.10	±1.10	±2.22	±1.32	±2.32	±3.63	±1.55

Among the tested solvents, the ethanol/water mixture (80:20) consistently outperformed water and ethyl acetate in both Trolox equivalents (TEAC) and TPC for all samples. This indicates that the ethanol/water mixture is the most effective solvent for extracting bioactive compounds such as phenolics and antioxidants. Ethyl acetate, on the other hand, demonstrated the lowest performance across the samples, which is expected given its lower polarity and limited ability to solubilize phenolic compounds. Water provided moderate extraction efficiency, but it was significantly less effective than the ethanol/water mixture.

The data also revealed that OL yielded the highest TEAC and TPC values across all solvents, particularly when extracted with ethanol/water, confirming their richness in antioxidants and phenolic compounds. In comparison, citrus peels (orange, lemon, and mixed) showed lower TEAC and TPC values, with mixed peels extracted with ethanol/water performing slightly better than individual peels, possibly due to synergistic effects among the different compounds present. Interestingly, while water extraction resulted in high yields for citrus peels, particularly LP, the extracted material contained relatively low antioxidant and phenolic content. This suggests that water extracted a substantial amount of non-phenolic hydrophilic compounds, such as sugars, rather than the desired bioactives.

The extraction yields (%EY) further supported the effectiveness of the ethanol/water mixture, which achieved the highest values for most samples. Ethyl acetate consistently produced the lowest yields, highlighting its limited applicability for these plant matrices. OL extracted with ethanol/water exhibited the highest antioxidant capacity (59.4 mg/g Trolox equivalents) and phenolic content (23.0 mg/g), making them the most potent source of bioactives under the tested conditions. Conversely, LP extracted with ethyl acetate showed the lowest values for both TEAC and TPC, indicating poor recovery of bioactives with this solvent.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the ethanol/water mixture is the optimal solvent for UAE of antioxidants and phenolics from these plant materials. OL, in particular, stand out as a superior source of bioactive compounds under these extraction conditions. Future studies may focus on further optimizing the ethanol/water ratio or adjusting extraction parameters to enhance bioactive recovery. Ethyl acetate may not be suitable for applications requiring high antioxidant or phenolic content, given its poor performance. Despite minor variations observed in some TEAC and TPC values, the low standard deviations across most measurements reflect consistency in the extraction process. This provides a strong basis for the reproducibility of the findings.

Determining antioxidant activity in spirulina and chlorella extracts using the DPPH method relies on maintaining a stable solution in which the extracted antioxidant compounds can react uniformly with the DPPH radical (Brand-Williams *et al.* 1995). However, when ethyl acetate is used as the extraction or dilution solvent, its limited polarity and poor miscibility with water can hinder the solubilization of antioxidant compounds—including phenolics, carotenoids, and other bioactive molecules—commonly present in microalgae (Goiris *et al.* 2012). This inadequate solubilization can lead to the formation of insoluble aggregates or precipitates, trapping the antioxidant compounds and preventing them from interacting evenly with the DPPH radicals.

As a result, the DPPH assay cannot accurately measure the radical-scavenging activity of the sample. Without a clear, stable solution, the reaction between the antioxidant compounds and the DPPH radicals is incomplete or inconsistent, yielding unreliable results. In short, using ethyl acetate as a solvent disrupts the intended assay conditions, causing precipitation and thus hindering the accurate determination of AA in spirulina and chlorella extracts.

The AA of essential oils, as measured in Trolox equivalents (TEAC, $\mu\text{mol/mL}$), demonstrates a significant variation across different plant sources (Table 25).

Table 25. Antioxidant activity of essential oils using TEAC assay

Essential Oil	$\mu\text{mol/mL}$
Eucalyptus <i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	0.319
Thyme <i>Thymus capitatus</i>	34.7
Rosemary <i>Rosemarinus officinalis</i>	0.794
Thyme <i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	12.7

Among the tested essential oils, *Thymus capitatus* (Thyme) exhibited the highest AA, with a TEAC value of 34.7 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$, indicating its potent antioxidant

potential. In comparison, *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme) displayed a much lower TEAC value of 12.7 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$, which, while still significant, highlights differences in antioxidant capacity within the same genus.

Rosemarinus officinalis (Rosemary) essential oil showed moderate AA, with a TEAC value of 0.794 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$, reflecting its known properties as a natural antioxidant source. In contrast, *Eucalyptus globulus* (Eucalyptus) had the lowest TEAC value of 0.319 $\mu\text{mol/mL}$, indicating relatively weaker AA compared to the other oils tested. These findings underline the variability in antioxidant capacity among essential oils, which can be attributed to differences in their chemical composition, particularly the presence and concentrations of phenolic and terpene compounds.

The extraction yields (EY%) and antioxidant activities, expressed in mg Trolox equivalents per gram of dry extract, of various plant materials were evaluated using different extraction methods and solvents. Ultrasound-assisted extraction (UAE) with water as the solvent yielded 38.0% for LP, 20.9% for OP, and 51.6% for a mixture of lemon and orange peels. The corresponding antioxidant activities were 13.1 mg/g, 21.4 mg/g, and 11.5 mg/g, respectively. These results suggest that while the mixed peels exhibited the highest extraction yield, their AA was lower than that of OP alone, indicating that higher yields do not necessarily correlate with increased AA.

Soxhlet extraction using ethyl acetate resulted in lower extraction yields: 4.0% for lemon peels, 11.6% for OP, and 20.5% for the mixed peels. However, the antioxidant activities were 21.5 mg/g, 12.9 mg/g, and 8.3 mg/g, respectively. Notably, LP extracted with ethyl acetate exhibited the highest AA despite the low yield, suggesting that ethyl acetate may selectively extract compounds with higher antioxidant potential.

PLE of OL using water achieved a remarkably high extraction yield of 318.30% with an AA of 15.8 mg/g. In contrast, using ethyl acetate as the solvent resulted in a significantly lower yield of 48.60% and an AA of 0.9 mg/g. This disparity indicates that water is more effective in extracting antioxidant compounds from OL, possibly due to the polarity of the bioactive compounds present.

For microalgae, the combination of UAE/MAE with water yielded 103.13% for spirulina and 45.79% for chlorella, with corresponding antioxidant activities of 5.1 mg/g and 53.3 mg/g, respectively. These findings highlight that chlorella not only had a higher AA but also a more efficient extraction process compared to spirulina. When ethyl acetate was used as the solvent, both the extraction yields and antioxidant activities were substantially lower for both microalgae species, underscoring the importance of solvent selection in the extraction process.

These observations are consistent with existing literature, which emphasizes the influence of extraction methods and solvents on the yield and AA of plant extracts. For instance, studies have shown that ultrasound-assisted extraction can enhance the recovery of phenolic compounds from citrus peels, leading to higher antioxidant

activities (Ana *et al.* 2018). Similarly, PLE has been reported to efficiently extract bioactive compounds from OL, with water proving to be a more effective solvent than ethyl acetate (Boli *et al.* 2022). The choice of solvent and extraction method is crucial in maximizing the yield and activity of antioxidants from various plant materials.

4.2 Antibacterial and antifungal activity of analysed extracts

Inhibitory activity of extracts against bacterial/fungal strains

To determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), the following bacterial strains were evaluated: *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 29213, *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Salmonella enterica* ATCC 14028, *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 29212, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, and *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292. Each strain was initially cultured in 10 mL of an appropriate sterile broth medium: Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) for *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa*; Nutrient Broth (NB) for *S. epidermidis*; and Tryptic Soy Yeast Extract (TSYE) for *L. monocytogenes*. Cultures were activated by incubating the broth tubes at 37 °C for 24 hours. The purity of each inoculum was verified via microscopic examination of Gram-stained smears. Following incubation, the spread plate technique was employed to inoculate agar plates with each microorganism from the respective broth cultures, ensuring adequate distribution and colony isolation. The bacterial morphology was subsequently confirmed through optical microscopy. To prepare for MIC testing, multiple colonies from each agar plate were transferred into a sterile saline solution (8.5 g/L NaCl), and the suspension was adjusted to achieve the turbidity of a 0.5 McFarland standard, corresponding to approximately 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL.

For assessing antifungal activity, the following fungal strains were utilized: *Candida parapsilopsis* ATCC 22019, *Aspergillus awamori* DSMZ 63272, *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 6275, *Rhizopus oligosporus* ATCC 22959, *Aspergillus brasiliensis* ATCC 16404, *Aspergillus terreus* DSMZ 23081, and *Actinomucor elegans* ATCC 22963. All strains were cultured on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) as the growth medium. To prepare the inoculum, a spore suspension at a concentration of 10^6 spores/mL were made by harvesting spores from dormant agar plates. For inoculation on PDA plates, 100 µL of the prepared spore suspension was evenly spread on the solidified agar surface using a sterile Drigalsky spatula to ensure uniform distribution. The spores were detached from the agar plates using a 0.1% Tween 80 solution and sterile glass beads to facilitate dispersion. The inoculated plates were then incubated at 30 °C for five days, allowing for the development of a consistent layer of black spores across the agar surface.

Determination of the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)

MIC was determined using a resazurin-based microtiter plate

antibacterial/antifungal assay. Essential oil stock solutions were prepared by mixing one part Tween 80 with eight parts 50% ethanol, while other samples were centrifuged and filtered through 0.45 µm membranes. In each well of a 96-well microtiter plate, 100 µL of sterile medium (specific to each microorganism) and 100 µL of the sample were added. Serial two-fold dilutions were performed across the wells of each row by transferring 100 µL from well to well, discarding 100 µL from the final well. To each well, 10 µL of inoculum was added, standardized to 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL for bacterial strains and 10^6 spores/mL for fungal strains. Gentamicin (0.04 mg/mL in saline solution) served as the positive control for bacteria, while Fluconazol (1.5 mg/mL in saline solution) was used as the positive control for fungi. Negative controls were prepared with a mixture of one part saline solution, eight parts 50% ethanol, and one part Tween 80 for essential oils, with solvent controls used for other samples. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for bacteria (20–22 hours) and at 30 °C for fungi (20–22 hours). After incubation, 20 µL of 0.2 mg/mL resazurin aqueous solution was added to each well, followed by an additional incubation period of 2 hours at 37 °C. MIC values were recorded as the lowest concentration at which no color change from blue to pink occurred, indicating complete inhibition of bacterial or fungal growth. Each sample was tested in duplicate to ensure accuracy.

Antibacterial activity before concentration of the citrus peels and olive leaves extracts

In Table 26 is illustrated the antibacterial activity of various citrus peels and olive leaves extracts before concentration (optimization) of the samples, expressed as their MIC against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, demonstrated significant variation depending on the extraction method, solvent used, and bacterial strain tested.

Table 26. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292 and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028 of citrus peels and olive leaves samples

Samples	Gram (+) Bacteria				Gram (-) Bacteria	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>
OL W S	6.250	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OL EA S	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
* OL W UAE	*n.b	1.250	*n.b	1.250	*n.b	*n.b
* OL EA UAE	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b
OL UAE/MAE W	3.125	n.b	3.125	n.b	n.b	3.125
OL UAE/MAE EA	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OP+LP UAE EA	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b

Table 26. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against: *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292 and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028 of citrus peels and olive leaves samples

Samples	Gram (+) Bacteria				Gram (-) Bacteria	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>
OP EA UAE/MAE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
LP EA UAE/MAE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OP+LP EA PLE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OP EA PLE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
LP EA PLE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OP + LP W UAE/MAE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OP W UAE/MAE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
LP W UAE/MAE	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b

n.b. – no bioactivity \leq 50 mg dry weight/mL; *n.b. – no bioactivity \leq 10 mg dry weight/mL; OP – orange peel; LP – lemon peel; W – water; EA – ethyl acetate; S – Soxhlet; UAE – ultrasound; UAE/MAE – ultrasounds+microwave; PLE – pressurized liquid extraction.

Among Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* were tested. Extracts produced using ultrasound and microwave-assisted methods (UAE/MAE) with water (W) as the solvent exhibited notable activity. The OLE UAE/MAE W extract showed moderate inhibition against *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, and *L. monocytogenes*, with MIC values of 3.125 mg/mL for each strain. This suggests that the combination of ultrasound and microwave enhances the recovery of bioactive compounds with antibacterial properties. Similar findings in the literature highlight the effectiveness of advanced extraction techniques in enhancing antibacterial efficacy, particularly against Gram-positive bacteria (Burt 2004).

Soxhlet water extracts (OLE W S) demonstrated inhibitory activity against *S. aureus* (6.250 mg/mL) but lacked efficacy against other tested Gram-positive bacteria. Ethyl acetate extracts, regardless of the method used, showed no bioactivity at MIC \leq 50 mg/mL, emphasizing the limited solubility of antibacterial compounds in semi-polar solvents like ethyl acetate. These results align with studies suggesting that polar solvents like water are more efficient in extracting hydrophilic antimicrobial compounds, particularly phenolic acids and flavonoids, which are effective against Gram-positive bacteria (Hayek 2014).

For Gram-negative bacteria, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Salmonella enterica*, the results were more limited. Among the extracts tested, only OLE W US exhibited bioactivity, with a MIC of 1.250 mg/mL against *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*. The effectiveness of ultrasound-assisted water extracts against these strains highlights the role of ultrasonication in disrupting cellular structures and enhancing the recovery of bioactive compounds (Chemat *et al.* 2017).

The absence of detectable antibacterial activity in most extracts may be due to insufficient concentrations of bioactive compounds in these samples. Dilution of active compounds during the extraction process or the inherently low concentrations of antimicrobials in certain plant materials could explain this lack of activity. Concentrating these extracts may help achieve the threshold levels required for antibacterial efficacy, as noted in previous studies where higher concentrations enhanced bioactivity (Mehmood *et al.* 2020).

The lack of activity in ethyl acetate extracts against Gram-negative bacteria is consistent with their higher resistance due to the outer membrane barrier, which reduces the permeability of hydrophobic compounds. This aligns with reports indicating that Gram-negative bacteria are generally less susceptible to phenolic compounds than Gram-positive bacteria due to structural differences in their cell walls (Silhavy *et al.* 2010).

The results underscore the critical role of extraction methods and solvents in determining the antibacterial efficacy of plant-based extracts. Water-based ultrasound and microwave-assisted methods demonstrated the most promising results, particularly for Gram-positive bacteria, suggesting their ability to recover hydrophilic bioactive compounds. Conversely, the lack of activity in ethyl acetate extracts highlights the limited solubility of antibacterial compounds in non-polar to semi-polar solvents, consistent with previous findings (Burt 2004; Hayek 2014).

The significant bioactivity of water-based extracts, especially those obtained using advanced techniques like ultrasound and microwave-assisted extraction, suggests their potential for use in natural antimicrobial formulations. Their moderate efficacy against Gram-negative bacteria further highlights their potential for broad-spectrum applications, albeit with limitations. The lack of activity in ethyl acetate extracts points to the importance of solvent selection in optimizing extraction for specific applications, such as food preservation or medicinal formulations.

Antibacterial activity after concentration of the citrus peels and olive leaf extracts based on the optimization Table 1

MIC data indicate that most extracts exhibited no detectable antibacterial activity (n.b.) against the tested bacterial strains at concentrations ≤ 0.2 mg dry weight/mL (Table 27).

Table 27. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292 and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028 of citrus peels, olive leaves and microalgae samples

Samples	Gram (+) Bacteria				Gram (-) Bacteria	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>
LP-UAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP UAE Ethanol 80%	*n.b	0.006	*n.b	0.013	*n.b	*n.b
OP-UAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-UAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OL-UAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OL UAE Ethanol 80%	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b
OL UAE EA Maceration 4 h	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OL UAE W Maceration 4 h	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OL-S-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-S-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-S-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-S-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-UAE/MAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-UAE/MAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-UAE/MAE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OL UAE/MAE W	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b
OL UAE/MAE EA	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b	n.b
OL-PLE-W	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-UAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-UAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-UAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OL-UAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-S-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-S-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-S-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OL-S-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-EA-PLE	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-PLE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
MIX LP+OP-PLE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
LP-UAE/MAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
OP-UAE/MAE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	0.050	n.b.	n.b.	0.050
MIX LP+OP-UAE/AE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	0.050	n.b.	n.b.	0.050
OL-PLE-EA	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.	n.b.
CHLORELLA-UAE/MAE-EA	*n.b.	*n.b.	*n.b.	*n.b.	*n.b.	*n.b.
SPIRULINA-UAE/MAE-EA	*n.b.	*n.b.	0.100	*n.b.	*n.b.	0.100

Table 27. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292 and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028 of citrus peels, olive leaves and microalgae samples

Samples	Gram (+) Bacteria				Gram (-) Bacteria	
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>
SPIRULINA UAE/MAE W	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b
CHLORELLA UAE/MAE W	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b	*n.b

n.b. – no bioactivity \leq 0.2 mg dry weight/mL; *n.b. – no bioactivity \leq 0.4 mg dry weight/mL; OP – orange peel; LP – lemon peel; W – water; EA – ethyl acetate; S – Soxhlet; UAE – ultrasound; MAE – microwave; UAE/MAE – ultrasounds+microwave; PLE – pressurized liquid extraction.

This lack of bioactivity was consistent across both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, regardless of the extraction method, solvent, or plant material used. However, specific extracts demonstrated notable antibacterial activity when prepared under certain conditions.

OP extracts obtained through UAE/MAE using ethyl acetate EA as the solvent (exhibited inhibitory effects against *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) at an MIC of 0.05 mg dry weight/mL. Similarly, a combined extract of lemon and orange peels prepared under the same conditions (MIX LP+OP-UAE/MAE-EA) showed identical MIC values against these bacterial strains. These findings suggest that UAE/MAE combined with EA effectively isolates bioactive compounds with broad-spectrum antibacterial properties. Ethyl acetate, a semi-polar solvent, is known to extract phenolic and terpenoid compounds that are effective against bacterial membranes (–Salam and Mostafa 2014).

Extracts from spirulina prepared via UAE/MAE with EA displayed antibacterial activity at a slightly higher MIC of 0.1 mg dry weight/mL against the same strains, indicating lower potency compared to citrus peel extracts. The observed activity could be attributed to bioactive compounds such as phenolic acids and carotenoids found in spirulina, which have been associated with antimicrobial properties (Martins *et al.* 2023).

The results underscore the importance of solvent polarity and extraction methods in isolating effective antimicrobial agents. Water-based extractions consistently showed no bioactivity, likely due to the solubility of antioxidant compounds rather than antibacterial agents. Ethyl acetate, on the other hand, demonstrated superior efficacy in isolating semi-polar compounds, which are often associated with antibacterial properties. Furthermore, advanced methods like UAE/MAE have been shown to disrupt plant cell walls effectively, enhancing the recovery of active compounds without significant degradation (Carreira-Casais *et al.* 2021).

These findings highlight the potential of UAE/MAE combined with ethyl acetate as a promising extraction strategy for isolating antimicrobial compounds from natural sources. These results have implications for developing natural antimicrobials for use in food preservation and pharmaceutical applications.

LP extracts prepared using UAE with ethanol (80%) as the solvent demonstrated measurable antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Listeria monocytogenes*, with MICs of 0.006 mg dry weight/mL and 0.013 mg dry weight/mL, respectively. The activity against *P. aeruginosa* (a Gram-negative bacterium) is particularly noteworthy, as Gram-negative bacteria are often more resistant to antimicrobial agents due to their complex outer membrane structure (Silhavy *et al.* 2010). The presence of bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, limonoids, and essential oils in LP likely contributes to this activity. Ethanol, being a polar organic solvent, may enhance the extraction of such compounds, which possess antibacterial properties (Burt 2004).

Extracts from chlorella and OL, regardless of the solvent or method used, exhibited no detectable bioactivity against the tested bacterial strains. This absence of activity suggests that the concentrations of antimicrobial compounds in these extracts were below the threshold required for efficacy under the tested conditions. For example, water-based extractions are highly effective for hydrophilic compounds, but these may not always possess significant antibacterial properties. Similarly, extracts prepared with ethyl acetate, a semi-polar solvent, failed to show activity, potentially indicating the absence or low solubility of key antimicrobial compounds in the tested matrices.

The observed differences in antibacterial activity highlight the importance of the extraction method and solvent in determining bioactivity. Ethanol (80%) was effective for the LP extract that exhibited activity, potentially due to its ability to dissolve both polar and non-polar compounds, leading to the recovery of a broader spectrum of bioactive compounds (Chemat *et al.* 2017).

The activity of LP extracts aligns with previous studies that have identified citrus peels as rich sources of phenolic compounds and essential oils with antimicrobial properties (Burt 2004; Matos *et al.* 2017). However, the lack of activity in olive leaf extracts contrasts with reports of strong antimicrobial properties in olive leaf phenolics, such as oleuropein, suggesting that extraction parameters may require further optimization to fully recover these compounds (Durmus *et al.* 2024).

The results underscore the critical role of extraction parameters, solvent choice, and sample concentration in determining the antimicrobial efficacy of plant-based extracts. While LP extracts showed promise against specific strains, further work is needed to optimize extraction methods and assess the antimicrobial potential of other materials, particularly OL and microalgae. Future studies should consider increasing

sample concentrations and refining assay conditions to enhance the detection of bioactivity.

Antibacterial activity of the bog bilberry leaf extracts

In Table 28 are illustrated the results for antibacterial effects of bog bilberry leaf extracts with HPE. Regarding Gram-positive bacteria, the extract exhibited the same MIC towards *S. aureus* and *S. enterica*, respectively, 8.75 mg/mL. The strains *E. faecalis*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. epidermidis* were the most resistant. The results showed no inhibitory effect against these strains.

Table 28. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus subsp. aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *E. faecalis* and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028 of bog bilberry leaves samples

Sample	Gram (+) Bacteria			Gram (-) Bacteria		
	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>E. faecalis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. enterica</i>
Bog bilberry HPE	8.750	n.d	n.d	n.d	n.d	8.750
Gentamicin	0.0001	0.0001	0.002	0.013	0.003	0.002

Antibacterial activity of the essential oils

In Table 29 below and Figure 40 are illustrated the MIC results for antibacterial activity of essential oils tested. All the EO shown antibacterial activity, with garlic and both thyme varieties expressing higher activity than the positive control, Fluconazol, against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*. According to the results obtained, garlic and conehead thyme followed closely by thyme shown the highest antibacterial effects against the tested strains.

Table 29. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Staphylococcus aureus subsp. aureus* ATCC 29213, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* ATCC 12228, *Listeria monocytogenes* DSMZ 115292 and *Salmonella enterica* (*S. typhimurium*) ATCC 14028

Sample	Initial concentration (µl/ml)	Strain					
		Gram negative bacteria (-)			Gram positive bacteria (+)		
		<i>E. Coli</i> ATCC 25922	<i>S. Enteric</i>	<i>P. Aeruginosa</i>	<i>L. Monocytogenes</i>	<i>S. Epidermidis</i>	<i>S. Aureus</i>

	a ATCC 14028	ATCC 27853	DSMZ 115292	ATCC 12228	ATCC 29213	MINIMUM INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (µl/ml)	
(5) Eucalipt	12,500	12,500	12,500	6,250	1,563	0,094	12,500
(6) Garlic	0,781	1,563	1,563	0,391	0,195	0,014	0,781
(7) Thyme	1,563	0,781	0,781	0,391	0,195	0,023	1,563
(8) Thyme conehead	0,781	0,391	0,391	0,391	0,098	0,014	0,781
(9) Rosemary	25,000	12,500	0,000	1,563	1,563	0,125	25,000
(C-) Saline solution + Tween 80 + EtOH (1:1:8)	-	-	12,500	12,500	12,500	-	-
(C+) Gentamicin 0.4 mg/ml	6,250	3,125	0,391	1,563	0,098	0,006	6,250

Figure 40. Resazurin-based microtiter plate antibacterial assay for essential oils (corresponding to Table 29)

Antifungal activity of the essential oils

The antifungal activity was performed for all the samples, however only the essential oils shown antifungal activity based on the resazurin method for fungal growth/absence. The analyses should be repeated, and the calculation should be performed based on optical density, as the resazurin method is not suitable for the

rest of the samples. In Table 30 below is illustrated the MIC results for antifungal activity of essential oils tested. All the EO shown antifungal activity, some of them even better activity than the positive control, Fluconazol.

Table 30. Minimum inhibitory concentration (mg dry weight/mL) against *Candida parapsilopsis* ATCC 22019, *Aspergillus awamori* DSMZ 63272, *Aspergillus niger* ATCC 6275, *Rhizopus oligosporus* ATCC 22959, *Aspergillus brasiliensis* ATCC 16404, *Aspergillus terreus* DSMZ 23081, and *Actinomyces elegans* ATCC 22963.

Sample	Initial concentration (µl/ml)	Fungal Strain						
		Gram negative bacteria (-)			Gram positive bacteria (+)			
		<i>C. parapsilopsis</i> ATCC 22019	<i>A. terreus</i> DSMZ 23081	<i>A. elegans</i> ATCC 22963	<i>R. oligosporus</i> ATCC 22959	<i>A. niger</i> ATCC 6275	<i>A. awamori</i> DSMZ 63272	<i>A. brasiliensis</i> ATCC 16404
INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (µl/ml)								
(5) Eucalipt	100	-	3,125	-	1,563	0,098	-	-
(6) Garlic	100	0,781	0,781	6,250	0,195	0,024	0,007	0,014
(7) Thyme	100	0,391	1,563	3,125	0,391	0,098	0,063	0,063
(8) Thyme conehead	100	0,098	6,250	0,781	0,781	0,195	0,078	0,078
(9) Rosemary	100	25,000	-	-	-	-	2,000	0,500
(C-) Saline solution + Tween 80 + EtOH (1:1:8)	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
(C+) Fluconazol 1.5 mg/ml	400	187,500	187,500	-	-	-	0,375	0,375

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, this study highlights the remarkable potential of Mediterranean plant and algal species, as well as select essential oils, as promising sources of bioactive phytobiotics with strong antioxidant and antimicrobial properties suitable for application in aquaculture and beyond. By systematically examining a wide range of matrices—including citrus peels (lemon, orange), olive leaves, bog bilberry leaves, microalgae (*Spirulina*, *Chlorella*), macroalgae (*Ulva*), and essential oils (e.g., garlic, thyme, rosemary, eucalyptus)—the research demonstrates that both extraction methodology and solvent selection play pivotal roles in maximizing the recovery of valuable compounds.

Green extraction methods, such as ultrasound-assisted, microwave-assisted, pressurized liquid, and high-pressure extraction, proved highly effective for isolating phenolic compounds, proteins, and pigments (chlorophylls, carotenoids, and phycocyanin) from plant and algal matrices. In particular, aqueous or aqueous-alcoholic solvents consistently outperformed less polar solvents, such as ethyl acetate,

in extracting phenolics and proteins, ensuring higher antioxidant activities and greater assay reliability. The use of water and ethanol–water mixtures facilitated the solubilization of phenolic compounds and proteins in spirulina, chlorella, and olive leaves, resulting in pronounced antioxidant effects as reflected by high TPC and strong Trolox Equivalent Antioxidant Capacity (TEAC) values.

Citrus peels emerged as robust sources of diverse phenolic compounds, with lemon and orange peels yielding high concentrations of flavonoids and phenolic acids known for their antioxidant and antimicrobial activities. Similarly, olive leaves, rich in oleuropein and related tyrosols, demonstrated that careful optimization of extraction parameters could enhance the recovery of potent bioactives. The microalgae *Spirulina* and *Chlorella* provided valuable pigments and proteins that contribute to antioxidant capacity, while *Ulva* and bog bilberry leaves yielded complex profiles of hydroxycinnamic acids, flavanols, and flavonols.

Notably, essential oils derived from garlic, thyme, rosemary, and eucalyptus also exhibited significant biological activities. Thyme essential oils, in particular, showed robust AA, while rosemary and garlic oils offered promising antimicrobial properties. The chemical diversity of these essential oils, rich in bioactive terpenes and sulfur compounds, underscores their value as natural preservatives and functional additives. Integrating essential oils into aquafeeds or other formulations could further enhance the health-promoting effects sought in antibiotic-free fish farming.

Although direct antimicrobial assessments revealed limited or no bioactivity in many crude extracts under the tested conditions, certain optimized extractions—especially those using ultrasound/microwave-assisted methods and semi-polar solvents—indicated the potential for effective antibacterial activity. Concentrating the extracts or adjusting the extraction parameters may reveal stronger inhibition effects against common bacterial and fungal pathogens in aquaculture. Moreover, the successful demonstration of antioxidant capacity, combined with select antimicrobial results, supports the strategic use of these extracts and essential oils as partial or complete substitutes for antibiotics in aquaculture feeds, thereby contributing to more sustainable and health-conscious farming practices.

Overall, this work provides clear evidence that Mediterranean flora and marine algae, alongside strategic extraction techniques and the incorporation of essential oils, can yield high-quality, bioactive phytobiotics. Such compounds, through their antioxidant and antimicrobial properties, hold promise for improving fish health, reducing disease prevalence, and cutting down antibiotic use. By refining extraction methods, solvent systems, and cultivation practices, the aquaculture industry can move toward more environmentally responsible, high-value products that support not only robust fish growth and immunity but also safer and healthier end-products for human consumption.

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